

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

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Summary

Improved soil health is important for multiple reasons, such as to achieve climate neutrality, or to stop desertification and biodiversity loss. The project NOVASOIL aims to promote soil health measures by identifying potential business models for farmers that allow remuneration for their implementation. The requirements that farmers must fulfil to participate in these business models are shaped by the underlying policies and regulations. This report provides results of tests that were conducted of the selected policy options and incentive mechanisms using Discrete Choice Experiments (DCEs). DCEs are widely used to analyse how farmers choose among contracts that demand more soil health-friendly production practices.

The DCEs were conducted in five case-studies looking at different business models and different policies or incentives. The Dutch case study, Rabo Carbon Bank, and one of the German case studies focus on the carbon credits trade for certified carbon removals. The Bulgarian case includes remuneration through the food value chain for wine produced with a focus on soil health. The second German case study focuses on an online marketplace (AgoraNatura) where farmers can finance the implementation of sustainable practices by selling certificates to other value chain actors (e.g., private investors and companies). The Italian case investigates the combination of incentives to stimulate carbon farming, for instance, through agri-environmental schemes and payments from carbon markets. The incentives and policies included in each study were determined through interviews and by conducting policy innovation labs (Task 4.2).

Key results per case-study are as follows:

- The Dutch case finds that farmers are unlikely to choose the presented hypothetical contracts, especially when no additional incentives besides the remuneration of the carbon credits are included (e.g., fixed cost shares, termination options for successors, annual training, or discounts on loans). The need for long-running contracts is evaluated as a crucial barrier. Including the option for farm successors to terminate the contract and discontinue carbon farming can help to motivate farmers to opt for longer contracts.
- The German case (TUM) shows that inflexible contracts with long duration and without guaranteed cost recovery are mostly rejected by farmers. Contracts should be more flexible but also more reliable. Farmers should have the option to terminate contracts when handing over to a successor. In addition, ancillary investment subsidies or free advice can increase the willingness to participate, especially for farmers who have not yet invested much in soil health. Considering the fluctuating price of carbon credits, a guarantee for farmers that costs of the carbon farming practices are covered is particularly relevant.

- The second German case (ZALF) finds that there is general interest of farmers to supply biodiversity and ecosystem services credits via an online marketplace. In addition, public seed-funding covering fixed costs for credits holds substantial value for farmers and may boost engagement by financially derisking participation. Finally, the use of artificial intelligence-based monitoring applications are valued by farmers.
- The Italian study reveals that farmers are hesitant to join soil conservation programs, especially when long-term programs involve significant income risks. Participation increases with higher per-hectare payments, while longer durations and additional effort reduce the likelihood of acceptance. To improve uptake, programs should offer greater flexibility, minimise perceived risks, and align better with farmers' economic priorities and expectations.
- This Bulgarian case shows that producers of traditional products (grapes, wine) can be motivated to implement soil-improving practices (especially cover crops) through a business model that targets improved quality of wine, and resulting increased opportunities and demand from wine tourism in Bulgaria.

General conclusions and recommendations can be derived from the results for each of the three main business models under consideration. First, carbon credit trade seems to be perceived as too risky, and especially the long durations of the contracts curb farmers' enthusiasm. Allowing hybrid payments that combine result-based and action-based payments, and including termination options to successors may help to overcome these barriers. Second, value chain initiatives are perceived positively by farmers in the experiments, and the literature. More flexibility and less strict requirements may help these favourable perceptions. It remains to be seen whether the upcoming EU regulation regarding sustainability labelling for the EU food sector may influence this. The third business model, public payments through agri-environmental schemes (AES) or eco-schemes, was not the primary focus of any of the case studies. However, public payments offer substantial funding, and their uptake can be improved, especially in countries with high opportunity costs. Furthermore, options of blended financing, combining public and private sources of remuneration, should be further investigated.

1 Objectives

The EU aims to improve the status of soil health, for instance, through the Green Deal or the Soil Monitoring law. Improved soil health is important for multiple reasons, such as to achieve climate neutrality, or to stop desertification and biodiversity loss. Currently, 60% of soils are in a poor condition. This is due, among others, to high management intensities of soils (European Commission, 2023). Research shows that farmers can be financially incentivised to farm less intensively and apply soil health measures (e.g., additional cover crops, grazing, agroforestry) (COWI et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2021). The project NOVASOIL aims to promote soil health measures by identifying potential business models for farmers that allow remuneration for their implementation.

Since soil health measures can potentially lead to carbon sequestration, carbon credit trade can offer a new business model for farmers. Besides this, soil health measures can be funded by the EU through eco-schemes or agri-environmental schemes (AES). Furthermore, private incentives such as payments over the food value chain for more environmentally friendly production can hold potential (McDonald et al., 2021). The requirements that farmers must fulfil to participate in these business models are shaped by the underlying policies and regulations. EU regulation 2024/3012 sets the requirements for certified carbon removals on arable land. Certified carbon removals will demand quantifiable, reliable long-term storage of carbon that results from measures above statutory requirements (European Commission, 2024). Considering value chain payments, the regulation on sustainability labelling for the EU food sector will be of interest. This regulation will aim for clear and trustworthy information on the environmental impact of products (Mengual et al., 2024). This deliverable will provide information on the effects of new incentives and policies related to these business models. A detailed overview of the business models, and their underlying regulations is provided in deliverable 2.2 of the project (Thiermann & Dries, 2024).

The case studies of the NOVASOIL project consider real-life setups of the business models. The Dutch case study Rabo Carbon Bank, and one of the German case studies focus on carbon credits trade for certified carbon removals, while the Bulgarian case includes remuneration through the food value chain for wine produced with a focus on soil health. The second German case study focuses on an online marketplace (AgoraNatura) where farmers can finance the implementation of sustainable practices by selling certificates. The Italian case focuses on incentives to stimulate carbon farming, for instance, through agri-environmental schemes. The incentives and policies included in each study were determined through interviews and by conducting policy innovation labs (Task 4.2).

The task underlying this report (Task 4.3) aimed to test the selected policy options and incentive mechanisms using Discrete Choice Experiments (DCE). DCEs are widely applied in micro-econometrics (Greene, 2018). They can be used, for instance, to

analyse how farmers choose among contracts that demand more soil health-friendly production practices. DCEs are considered particularly useful as participants can be presented with alternatives that are hypothetical and do not yet exist (Train, 2009). This was considered useful as Task 4.3 seeks to analyse the potential of new policy options and incentive mechanisms. The report presents the results of the DCEs for the Dutch, German, Italian, and Bulgarian cases and derives joint conclusions relevant for policy.

The remainder of the report presents the key features of the case studies in section 2. The main features of DCE and the results of the performed DCEs per case study are presented in section 3. Section 4 discusses the results, before deriving joint conclusions on the effectiveness of the new policy and incentive mechanisms.

2 Overview of the case studies & the case study incentives

This section summarizes the key features of each case study, and the relevant policies and incentives that were identified through interviews with key stakeholders and during the policy innovation labs.

2.1 WU – The Netherlands

Rabo Carbon Bank is a private initiative by Rabobank that remunerates farmers for generating carbon credits through sustainable soil management practices. Sustainable soil management practices enhance soil health while capturing carbon. The sequestered carbon amounts are then quantified and traded as carbon credits. The bank advises farmers on sustainable soil management practices and connects them with large companies (e.g., agribusiness firms) that seek to buy carbon credits to offset their CO₂ emissions.

The results from the interviews and the policy innovation lab suggest that financial incentives generated by selling carbon credits may not be sufficient to encourage widespread participation of farmers. This is particularly due to the relatively low carbon amount that is expected to be captured. In addition, the ambitious requirements set in EU regulation 2024/3012 for the certification of measures that lead to carbon sequestration in agriculture (carbon farming), were viewed as barriers and the participants in the interviews raised doubts about farmers' willingness and ability to meet the requirements. These requirements for achieving certified carbon credits are referred to as the *quality criteria*. They demand a robust quantification process, additionality (measures must exceed statutory requirements), long-term storage of CO₂, and the applied measures must have a positive (or at the minimum a neutral) impact on other sustainability objectives.

The DCE conducted for the case study explores farmers' willingness to opt for carbon farming contracts that aim at generating carbon credits that meet the quality criteria. The attributes of the hypothetical contracts did not only consider the quality criteria. Some of the attributes also referred to other promising incentives (e.g., training on sustainable soil management, discounts on loans, termination options for successors). These are hypothesised to positively influence farmer participation rates, following the outcomes of the interviews with key stakeholders.

The results of WU's DCE are detailed in section 3.2 of this report.

2.2 TUM - Germany

The Technical University of Munich (TUM) conducted a DCE in connection to the case study **CO₂-Land**. CO₂-Land is a carbon farming initiative in southwestern Germany that generates carbon credit certificates through soil carbon sequestration on partner farms. The initiative creates CO₂ sinks in arable soils, with farmers committing to

increasing soil organic carbon over time. The sale of climate certificates helps to compensate farmers for their efforts in building up additional soil organic matter.

The results from the interviews and the policy innovation lab identified potential barriers for farmers to participate in this business model. These barriers are also found in the literature, such as, uncertain price developments that fail to guarantee cost recovery, high upfront investment costs, and long-term commitments that limit flexibility in farm management, and a lack of awareness about the on-farm benefits of carbon farming practices. TUM's DCE builds on existing knowledge about these barriers by exploring incentives in these business models that are designed to address and overcome them.

The results of TUM's DCE are detailed in section 3.3 of this report.

2.3 ZALF – Germany

AgoraNatura is Germany's first online marketplace for voluntary and certified nature biodiversity and ecosystem services credits, where farmers are remunerated by interested donors/investors (such as private citizens or private companies). The remuneration is based on a crowdfunding mechanism. Moreover, the credit is only issued (i.e. sold) once it has received sufficient funding for successful realisation. Furthermore, the credits are externally certified under the Naturplus-Standard to ensure its ecological impact and transparency.

With regards to farmers, the marketplace empowers them to develop their own ideas on nature conservation measures substantiating credits. The farmers determine both the specific design of the measures and the amount of remuneration. Importantly, these certificates can generate profit for them, rather than merely offsetting revenue losses from decreased yield.

The incentives tested in the DCE were chosen based on the policy innovation lab, literature review as well as practical and past experiences from the AgoraNatura marketplace which showed: 1) a major barrier for farmer participation in privately financed and market-based nature conservation credits are initial fixed costs for conceptualising and certifying credits and their associated risk to become sunk costs, and 2) monitoring environmental improvements of credits could be innovated through AI-based monitoring technologies. The latter incentive (or attribute) was informed by a literature review on the technological developments of AI-based monitoring applications since studies or evidence on farmer preferences in this context are to date not available.

The results of ZALF's DCE are detailed in section 3.4 of this report.

2.4 UNIFE - Italy

The coastal area of the Emilia-Romagna Region is an area with a strong agricultural vocation with high-quality horticultural production. However, soil health faces strong pressures due to the high share of sand components and salinisation, subsidence, and loss of organic matter and contamination. Therefore, the case investigates the possibility of introducing **carbon farming** that can enhance organic matter, and develop a **Biodistrict**, where new business models aiming for remuneration of the measures through certification and production standards can be tested.

The case study found that the introduction of carbon farming measures (e.g. additional cover crops and wider crop rotations) could successfully increase soil organic carbon contents, water retention capacities, and soil biodiversity in the midterm. Next, the possibility to sell carbon credits was discussed during the policy innovation lab. Results show that uncertainty about the then-upcoming regulation 2024/3012, and risks entailed with carbon credit trade limited farmers' interest in the business model.

A possible solution discussed was to allow for combinations of CAP payments e.g. for agri-environmental schemes and payments from carbon markets. CAP payments are often action-based and farmers receive a guaranteed payment for the measures implemented, while payments from carbon markets will be result-based and depend on the amount of carbon stored. Hybrid payments combine both result-based and action-based payments and allow to mitigate risks. They are one of the tested incentives in the Italian case.

The results of UNIFE's DCE are detailed in section 3.5 of this report.

2.5 NBU - Bulgaria

The Bulgarian case study investigates the **Bulgarian Wine** Sector Program. The program manages the country's viticultural potential by regulating vineyard planting, replanting, and eradication. The 2021–2023 Program for Local and Regional Traditional Products aims to strengthen the link between traditional wine products and local communities, fostering economic and agricultural development. Additionally, local wine farmers should be encouraged to adopt soil health promoting practices—such as buffer strips, mulching, and non-productive crops—to combat soil erosion. The DCE focuses on financial incentives for one specific agri-environmental measure - **cover crops** in inter-rows - as a way to reduce erosion and improve soil health.

The results of the Bulgarian DCE are presented in section 3.6.

3 Results of the Discrete Choice Experiments

This section summarizes the theory behind DCE, before presenting the results of the case studies.

3.1 DCE in a Nutshell

DCEs present participants with a set of alternatives to choose from, these alternatives are called choice sets. They usually present attributes of a business model that might be relevant for the choice in a table. The attributes' levels vary systematically over a certain number of choice sets. The attributes relevant to the DCEs in this project might be, the measures farms are demanded to apply, or payments they might expect.

In the DCE the participants i reveal something about their preferences by making choices. The theory behind DCE is the random utility theory, and the choices observed are assumed to be affected by observable aspects z_{ij} (e.g. contract attributes), and unobservable aspects (ε_{ij}). The estimators β_j in equation 1 show how the utility of alternative j (U_{ij}) is impacted by the alternative's attributes (z'_{ij}):

$$U_{ij} = z'_{ij}\beta_j + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (1)$$

The level of utility is not directly observable, only the choice of a certain alternative is. These observed choices take the values zero when an alternative is not chosen, or a one when an alternative is chosen. Therefore, logistic regressions are applied for the analysis of the underlying data (Greene, 2018). Equation 2 shows that the predicted probability to observe a choice of alternative j reflects the probability that alternative j has the highest utility among all J alternatives presented (Train, 2009). Equation 2 shows the predicted probabilities in the conditional logit model:

$$Prob_{ij} = \frac{\exp(z'_{ij}\beta_j)}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp(z'_{ij}\beta_j)} \quad (2)$$

The coefficients provide insights into which aspects the participants perceive positively or negatively. However, these estimators do not provide information on how much value participants assign to the attributes. Therefore, Willingness-to-pay (WTP) or willingness-to-accept (WTA) can be estimated. Willingness-to-pay is more commonly used in consumer research and shows how much a consumer is willing to pay for a positively perceived aspect (or how much discount the participant would demand to accept a negatively perceived attribute) (Greene, 2018).

WTA values refer to situations where participants receive payment and do not pay for a good or service. Such payments might be granted by agri-environmental schemes for the implementation of soil health measures. The WTA values show, for instance, how much of a payment per hectare a farmer is willing to sacrifice, for instance, to receive annual training. Both values (WTP and WTA) are calculated from the ratio of the coefficients of interest (Greene, 2018):

$$WTA = \frac{\beta_{training}}{\beta_{payment}}$$

The values provide valuable insights for politicians. Villanueva et al. (2017), for instance, estimated farmers' preferences to participate in AES that demanded more cover crops and increases in the ecological focus areas. The calculation of WTA values allowed the authors to display the compensational requests farmers have for the implementation of soil health-improving practices.

3.2 The Netherlands (WU) - Would Dutch Farmers opt for Hypothetical Carbon Farming Contracts?

3.2.1 Synthesis of the results

Title: Would Dutch Farmers opt for Hypothetical Carbon Farming Contracts?

Authors : Insa Thiermann, Steven van der Maarel, Liesbeth Dries

Structured Abstract: **Context** - The European Union (EU) sets ambitious goals for CO₂ reductions. In this context, politicians show increasing interest in soil health because healthy soils with a higher organic matter content store carbon. Carbon credits can result from 'carbon farming' and can be traded on carbon markets, offering new income opportunities to farmers. To prevent greenwashing, the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU/2024/3012) establishes quality criteria and lays down monitoring and reporting processes for certifying carbon removals and carbon farming. **Objective** - This article explores whether Dutch farmers would opt for hypothetical carbon farming contracts that aim at generating carbon credits fulfilling the quality criteria of the CRCF (quantification, additionality, long-term storage, sustainability). **Method** - The Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) underlying the analysis considers the quality criteria in the management requirements of the hypothetical contracts (additionality, quantification, sustainability) and the attributes of the contracts (long-term storage). **Results & Conclusion** - We find that Dutch farmers are unlikely to choose the presented hypothetical contracts. The predicted probability of choosing a contract is estimated to be 40% for the mixed logit model, and only 12% when no additional incentives besides the remuneration of the carbon credits are included (e.g., fixed cost shares, termination options for successors, annual training, or discounts on loans). The need for long-running contracts is evaluated as a crucial barrier. However, including the option for farm successors to terminate the contract and discontinue carbon farming can help to motivate farmers to opt for longer contracts.

Key Words: carbon credits, carbon farming, discrete choice, farmer preferences, soil health

Case study: Rabo Carbon Bank

Incentives tested: payments for carbon credits, fixed cost shares, termination options for successors, annual training, or discounts on loans

Policy considered: EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU/2024/3012)

3.2.2 Introduction

Topsoils in the EU store 14 billion tons of carbon, which is equivalent to 51 billion tonnes of CO₂ equivalents. This is much more than what is annually emitted by EU member states (European Commission, 2018). Studies claim that adjustments in soil management practices can result in additional carbon removals, help to offset emissions, and reach net zero emissions by 2050 (Günther et al., 2024; McDonald et al., 2021). Soil health and carbon removals can be increased by applying more extensive farming practices, for instance, by reducing tillage, using additional cover and catch crops or converting arable land to grassland (COWI et al., 2021; McDonald et al., 2021). Carbon removal activities on farmland are commonly referred to as carbon farming measures (European Commission, 2024).

Soil health in the EU is currently considered to be poor (European Commission, 2023b), and the soil carbon removal potential of farmland is not sufficiently used. Generating certified carbon credits through carbon farming is a relatively new concept in the EU and might help motivate farmers to implement extensive practices. Carbon credits, or certified carbon removals, can be traded on voluntary carbon markets (European Energy Exchange, 2025). The EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU/2024/3012) seeks to ensure high quality carbon removals by establishing a certification and registration system that avoids greenwashing (European Commission, 2024). The CRCF quality criteria summarise the requirements for certified carbon removals - Carbon removals should be quantified accurately and robustly, should generate a net carbon removal benefit that is additional, should ensure long-term storage of carbon, and have at least a neutral impact or offer co-benefits for other sustainability objectives (European Commission, 2024).

This article analyses Dutch farmers' preferences for hypothetical carbon farming contracts that fulfil the requirements in regulation EU/2024/3012. Farmers in the study were informed about the expected carbon removal amounts for representative Dutch farms, as determined through simulation by Kik et al. (2024), and Matis (2023). Learning more about Dutch farmers' preferences is useful because private carbon farming schemes were developed even before the drafting and finalization of the CRCF regulation. Therefore, current carbon farming contracts often do not meet the CRCF quality criteria. The farmer organisation ZLTO, for instance, offered carbon farming contracts of five years only and farmers did not need to meet the additionality criterion (Bartolini et al., 2024). In addition, articles on the topic that focus on the EU (e.g., Aslam et al., 2017; Block et al., 2024), and especially those that consider the new legislative framework, are still scarce. Furthermore, concrete information on the to-be-expected carbon removals for measures on arable land and the to-be-expected payments are rarely presented to farmers. This study uses a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) to elicit farmers' preferences for hypothetical contracts and their perception of specific contract attributes (Hensher et al., 2015).

The report is structured as follows. First, the quality criteria of the CRCF regulation are summarised in section 2. Next, the design and the analysis of the DCE are described (section 3). Section 4 presents the results. Section 5 provides a discussion.

3.2.3 Requirements for EU certified carbon credits

First, quantification requires that carbon removals should be quantified in a relevant, accurate, complete, consistent, transparent and comparable manner. During quantification, the net carbon removal benefit should be computed following two steps: in the first step, the gross amount of additional carbon removals that a carbon removal activity has generated in comparison to a baseline is calculated. Standardised baselines should be used that reflect the standard performance of comparable farms in similar social, economic, environmental, and technological circumstances and geographical locations. (European Commission, 2024). Next, to quantify the net carbon removal, any increase in greenhouse gas emissions related to the implementation of the carbon farming measure should be deducted (European Commission, 2024). Second, to ensure beneficial effects for the overall emissions, carbon farming measures should be additional. Therefore, activities should go beyond EU and national statutory requirements, and the incentive effect of the certification is necessary to make the activity financially viable (European Commission, 2024). Third, carbon storage should be permanent or is aimed at storing carbon over the long-term. This also implies monitoring rules and liability in case of reversals. (European Commission, 2024). Finally, carbon farming is assumed to have the potential to not only mitigate climate change but also to deliver co-benefits for sustainability. Therefore, minimum sustainability requirements are introduced that ensure that carbon farming measures have at least a neutral impact or generate co-benefits for other sustainability objectives (e.g., biodiversity, protection of water and marine resources, pollution prevention). (European Commission, 2024).

3.2.4 Methodology

3.2.4.1 Selection of measures

The selected carbon farming measures in the hypothetical contracts ensure the fulfilment of the CRCF quality criteria (European Commission, 2024). The measures were chosen based on the existing literature. Kik et al. (2024) developed the programme Farm Analytics, which identifies sustainable soil management strategies that maximise the expected profit of a crop farm in the long term, while meeting certain soil quality goals using Mixed-Integer-Linear Programming. In addition, the authors provide information about the optimal strategies for Dutch farms. The farms either worked extensively (farms with standard arable crops) or intensively (farms with potatoes, carrots or onions) on clay or sandy soils and were representative of the Netherlands. Building on this, Matis (2023) used the RothC model by Rothamsted

Research (2024) to calculate the carbon removals that result from these soil health measures.

Both Kik et al. (2024) and Matis (2023) present results for farms that would continue standard farm management, and for farms implementing soil quality-oriented management strategies. Kik et al. (2024) find the following optimal strategies: for intensive farms with high-value arable crops (onions, carrots, and potatoes), a minimum share of 25 % of the crop rotation needs to include grains (incl. corn), farms are required to at least use 100 kg N/ha from organic sources, i.e. cattle manure or compost, and farmers must plant cover crops whenever possible, meaning that there are at least eight weeks between harvesting one crop and seeding another. For extensive farms with standard arable crops, the income maximising strategy that allows to reach soil health is a minimum share of 50% of the crop rotation needs to be grains, farms are also required to at least use 100 kg N/ha from organic sources and farmers must also plant cover crops whenever possible.

The carbon removal amounts resulting from these requirements are relatively low: for intensive farms on clay soils with soil-quality-oriented management, Matis (2023) calculates an additional removal in comparison to farms applying standard management practices of 0.27 tons of carbon equivalents per hectare per year. For farms farming intensively on sandy soils, the amount is 0.7 tons of carbon equivalents per hectare per year. Overall, the indicated values appear to be in line with other estimations (McDonald et al., 2021. Lessmann et al., 2022).

To adequately inform farmers in our survey, the amounts found by Matis (2023) were provided to both intensive and extensive farmers, as Matis does not provide amounts for extensive farms separately. When farmers stated to operate on loam or loess soils, they were provided with an average of the sequestered amounts. The management requirements depended on their level of intensity.

The quantification criterion foresees that the carbon amount sequestered should be determined with respect to a standardised baseline (European Commission, 2024). The comparison of soil organic carbon removals from adjusted farm management practices with carbon removals from standard management practices provides such a baseline. Using the comparison to standard Dutch farms also fulfils the additionality criterion. Neither the CAP nor the Dutch legislation hold a minimum requirement for grain shares in crop rotations. The enhanced conditionality of the CAP foresees crop rotation and diversification (GAEC (good agricultural and environmental conditions) 7), but this only prescribes a change in primary crops and limits the share of the main crop. The requirement of a minimum amount of soil cover (GAEC 6) is less strict than in Kik et al. (2024). Finally, only a maximum amount is defined for the usage of organic fertilisers. In 2024, this maximum amount became 170 kg N per hectare in the Netherlands (European Commission, 2023a). Furthermore, Kik et al (2024) developed

strategies that meet soil quality indicators and hence ensure that the sustainability criterion is fulfilled.

Besides arable farmers, our survey also includes farmers that mainly have grassland and work on mineral soils. Günther et al. (2024) evaluate the effects of carbon farming measures and explain that grasslands are potential carbon sinks but turn into carbon sources when managed too intensively. The requirements presented to these farmers were derived from programs for meadow bird protection (more organic fertiliser, extensive grazing, resting periods, and no ploughing), which is important for the Netherlands (Boerennatuur, 2023; Tanis et al., 2020). Farmers with grassland on mineral soils were also presented with the removal potential calculated by Kik et al. (2024) and Matis (2023), and received the information that precise amounts for grassland are not available yet.

3.2.4.2 Attribute selection, design & conduct of the DCE

The attributes of the DCE and their levels were chosen based on articles determining farmer preferences for agri-environmental schemes (AES) focused on soil health measures or carbon farming contracts. The first two attributes of the DCE refer to the monetary aspect. One is the carbon credit price on offer. It varied between € 10 and € 50 per carbon credit (per ton of CO₂). € 25 per carbon credit represents current carbon prices. The upper bound of € 50 per carbon credit was offered in a trial of the Interreg carbon farming project (Demeyer et al., 2022).

The second monetary attribute is a fixed cost share. In some hypothetical contracts, farmers received a fixed compensation of up to 100% of the cost of applying the measures. In other contracts, they received no fixed compensation, these display contracts where compensation is only foreseen through carbon markets. A fixed cost share for the applied measures was included because farmers can oppose riskier, purely result-based payments (Herzon et al., 2018).

The next attribute is contract duration. When deciding to choose a hypothetical carbon farming contract, farmers needed to commit for at least 10 years (long-term storage). (Rochecouste et al., 2017) point out that some farmers may be particularly critical toward long contracts because they limit flexibility for their successors. To grant successors more flexibility, special termination options are commonly included in contracts when children take over the business (e.g., insurance contracts or contract farming agreements) (UNIDROIT et al., 2015) and were added to the DCE's attributes.

The last attribute is 'support for sustainable soil management'. This support is defined as an annual training on carbon farming practices or being granted cheaper credit rates for all loans of the company. The first additional support incentive was included as Schaub et al. (2023) show that training opportunities can effectively motivate farmers. Furthermore, Demeyer et al. (2022) identify a lack of finance as a hindrance for farmers to choose carbon farming contracts.

The attributes and their corresponding levels are presented in Table 3.2.1. To create the experimental design, the *dcreate* package in Stata, as described by Hole (2016) was utilized. Designs for DCEs are statistically derived. This process ensures model identification while minimising collinearity among attributes and levels (Reed Johnson et al., 2013). The resulting design achieved a D-efficiency of 96 % and consisted of nineteen choice cards.

Table 3.2.1. Attributes chosen for the discrete choice experiment.

Attribute	Levels ^a
Compensation of costs (%)	0% , 25%, 50%, 75%, 100%
Carbon credit price	€0 per ton^a , €10 per ton, €20 per ton, €30 per ton, €40 per ton, €50 per ton
Contract duration	0 years^a , 10 years, 20 years, 30 years
Termination option (for successors)	Yes, No
Support for sustainable soil management	none , annual training on sustainable management, 0.5% discount on new farm loans

^aThe levels used for the none-option are in bold. For carbon credit prices and contract durations the none-option levels are only expressed in the third alternative (no contract).

The survey was set up online on the platform Qualtrics. The data collection for the experiment started in April 2024 and ended in January 2025. Seven choice cards were randomly assigned to each participating farmer. On the choice cards, farmers were always offered two hypothetical contracts with varying attributes and a third, no-contract option. An example of one of the choice cards is provided in Figure 3.2.1 (in Dutch). Following the choice cards, farmers were asked to answer questions about themselves and their farms.

	Alternatief 1	Alternatief 2	Alternatief 3
% compensatie kosten	0%	50%	Geen deelname
Koolstofkrediet prijs	50 €	30 €	
Contractduur	10 jaar	30 jaar	
Optie beëindiging	Ja	Nee	
Steun duurzaam beheer	Training	-0.5% korting op leningen	

Figure 3.2.1. Example of one of the choice cards used for the survey.

3.2.4.3 Estimation

For the estimation, a mixed logit model and a latent class model (LCM) were estimated. The mixed logit model assumes that respondents (i) select the most attractive alternative from a set of J alternatives. The utility of choosing an alternative (U_{ij}) depends on the contract's attributes and their observed levels, represented by a vector x_{ij} , and an independently distributed random term (ε_{ij}). Individual-specific coefficients β_i determine the effect of the attributes on the utility (Eq. 1):

$$U_{ij} = \beta_i x_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (1)$$

The mixed logit model assumes that estimators are continuously distributed with density $f(\beta|\theta)$, where θ represents the distribution parameters. The probability of choosing a contract, as shown in Equation (2), becomes an integral over β values and is determined by simulation. In the end, the coefficients display the weighted average of the participant's preferences:

$$P_{ij} = \int \frac{\exp(\beta x_{ni})}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp(\beta x_{ij})} (\beta) f(\beta|\theta) d\beta \quad (2)$$

While the mixed logit accounts for preference heterogeneity using individual-specific coefficients, it lacks detailed information on differences in attribute perception (Train, 2009). Therefore, an LCM was also estimated. In LCM, the same coefficients are estimated per class. Besides this, the LCM presents estimates for the farmer and farm characteristics and displays how they affect class membership (Greene & Hensher, 2003). Willingness-to-accept (WTA) values were computed for both the mixed logit and LCM. WTA measures the rate of substitution between an attribute and monetary value (Train, 2009). In models with random effects, calculating the ratio directly would

lead to unreasonably high values (Train & Weeks, 2015), hence the price coefficient was considered as fixed when calculating WTA for the mixed logit model.

3.2.5 Results

3.2.5.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 3.2.2 shows the descriptive statistics.

Table 3.2.2. Descriptive statistics of the analysed sample.

Variable	mean	S.D.	Description
Hectares	90.13	124.47	Total farm area in hectares (sum of arable and grassland)
Hectares arable land	71.19	126.87	Arable land in hectares
Hectares grassland	18.94	32.21	Grassland in hectares
Sand	0.29	0.46	The predominant soil type is sand
Clay	0.43	0.50	The predominant soil type is clay
Loam	0.02	0.14	The predominant soil type is loam
Loess	0.01	0.10	The predominant soil type is loess
Grassland	0.24	0.43	The farm has grassland only
Intensive management	0.37	0.48	Farm is classified as intensive ^a
Organic	0.06	0.24	The farm is certified as organic, or in transition
Fulltime	0.82	0.39	The farm is a full-time operation
Arable farms	0.48	0.50	The farm is an arable farm only, and has no other branches of production, e.g. livestock husbandry
AES – soil health	0.17	0.38	The farmer participates in AES to improve soil health on grassland or arable land
Soil-health-friendly	0.51	0.50	The farm applies soil health-friendly management ^b
Share of rented farmland	30.86	30.31	Share of rented farmland
Year of birth	1969.38	13.47	Year the farmer was born
Higher education	0.44	0.50	Share of farmers with higher education (HBO (<i>Hoger beroepsonderwijs</i>) or university degree)
Succession	0.77	0.42	The farm will stay in business for at least the next ten years (run by the farmer or a successor)
Statement – Climate	3.52	0.91	Farmer's level of agreement with 'Climate change impacts my farm negatively' ^c
Statement - Productivity	4.35	0.77	Farmer's level of agreement with 'Soil health is important for my farm's productivity' ^c
Statement - Risks	2.87	1.02	Farmer's level of agreement with 'To achieve profit maximation - I am more willing to take risks than others' ^c
Participants	95		

^a For grassland(dairy)-only farms this included a self-classification. For arable and mixed farms this evaluation depends on the crops included in crop rotations. Following Kik et al. (2024) intensive farms have onions, carrots, and/or potatoes in their crop rotation.

^b Soil health-friendly management is assumed when arable farmers already display grain shares exceeding the hypothetical contract requirements, or when farmers with grassland offer grazing.

^c Farmers' opinions on these statements were evaluated using Likert scales. On these scales, 1 indicated full disagreement and 5 indicated full agreement.

3.2.5.2 Results from the Mixed Logit Estimation

Table 3.2.3 contains the results from the mixed logit estimation. The coefficients display which attributes significantly impact farmers' choices for a hypothetical carbon farming contract. The pseudo-R² of the model is 0.438. The predicted probability for farmers to choose a hypothetical contract is estimated to be 40 %. The coefficients in the model were chosen based on a likelihood ratio test or a robust Wald-test.

Table 3.2.3. Mixed logit model to explain farmer's decision for a carbon farming contract.

	Coef.	SD. Error	S.D.	SD. Error
Interaction effects				
ASC * Sand	6.983**	(2.859)		
ASC * Grassland	-9.638**	(4.692)		
ASC * Hectares	-0.051**	(0.024)		
ASC * Intensive mgmt.	-14.32**	(5.638)		
ASC * Fulltime	-5.409**	(2.560)		
ASC * AES – soil health	7.888**	(3.536)		
ASC * Soil health-friendly	10.74**	(4.541)		
ASC* Share rented farmland	-0.038	(0.024)		
ASC *Higher education	6.186**	(2.425)		
ASC * Succession	-2.461	(1.686)		
ASC * Climate	3.900**	(1.587)		
Contract attributes				
Compensation of costs (%)	0.199**	(0.0815)	0.138***	(0.0537)
Carbon credit price	0.188***	(0.0708)	0.159***	(0.0574)
Contract duration	-0.671***	(0.250)	0.480***	(0.179)
Termination option	8.058**	(3.165)	-8.523***	(3.257)
Support – annual training	4.041**	(1.773)	7.676***	(2.678)
Support– discount loans	1.974*	(1.138)	5.967**	(2.584)
ASC	-28.63**	(11.67)	15.28***	(5.757)
Observations	1,995			
Pseudo-R²	0.438			

The more productive soil types clay, loam and loess serve as the base category.

Standard errors in parentheses.

* p<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

Farmers display a higher predicted probability to choose a contract when the fixed compensation of costs and when the carbon credit price is expected to be higher. They oppose longer contract durations but value the termination option for successors. Furthermore, the coefficients show that the additional support for sustainable soil management (cheaper loans and training) has an effect: even though they are significant at a low level only (* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$).

The farm and farmer characteristics were included as interaction effects with an alternative specific constant (ASC). When two alternatives are very similar, the inclusion of one instead of two ASCs is commonly recommended (Auspurg & Liebe, 2011). The ASC used in the model is one for hypothetical carbon farming contracts and zero for alternatives representing the no-contract option. Such an ASC can also provide information about the perception of the hypothetical contracts that may not be captured by the attributes (Train, 2009). The ASC in the model is significantly negative, this indicates that farmers perceive the offer of carbon farming contracts as rather unattractive for reasons not explained by the attributes.

The interaction effects provide information on which farmers are more or less likely to choose a carbon farming contract. Unsurprisingly, the interaction effects with the variables 'Soil health friendly' or 'AES - soil health' are significantly positive, showing the relevance of how close farmers already are to fulfilling the requirements. In addition, farmers who classified themselves as intensive, larger, and fulltime farmers are less likely than extensive, smaller, parttime farms to participate. Furthermore, farmers on sandy soils, that agree more strongly with the statement 'Climate change impacts my farm negatively' and farmers with higher education are more likely to accept a contract.

3.2.5.3 Results from the LCM

The standard deviations of the attributes in Table 3.2.3 are all significantly positive. This indicates a heterogeneous perception of the attributes, which is explored further in an LCM (Table 3.2.4). Based on the BIC, a model with three classes is preferred. The first preference class has a high predicted probability of 86 % to choose a contract. The second preference class displays a predicted probability to choose a contract of only 4 % (uninterested in the offer). The third preference class is less certain about their perception of the contracts and has a predicted probability of 32 %. Considering the class shares, most farmers (42 %) are in class 2 ('uninterested'), 38 % are in class 1 ('interested'), and 20 % are in class 3 ('uncertain').

Comparing the perception of the contract attributes. Class 1 farmers display preferences like those already described for the mixed logit. They are motivated by higher carbon credit prices, higher fixed payments, the offer of termination options for successors, and the support through annual training. However, they dislike long

contract durations. Interestingly, long-running contracts would be accepted by the class 3 farmers. As the other classes, farmers in class 3 also value higher prices for carbon credits and a higher fixed cost share. They also value the option to receive a discount on loans and annual training. The uninterested class 2 farmers strongly oppose long contract durations, and only some positive effects are found for the carbon credit price and the fixed compensation of costs.

The second part of the table holds the class membership regression and displays which characteristics make farmers more likely to be part of the classes. They are interpreted with respect to the third preference class. Farmers in class 1 show a tendency to farm on grassland only. In addition, they are less likely to already apply soil health-friendly management practices. They tend to be younger and have a higher level of education than class 3 farmers. They further agree more strongly that soil health is important for the farm's productivity and consider themselves more willing to take risks. Their lower share of rented farmland might make it easier for these farmers to accept contracts. Class 2 farmers are uninterested in the contracts and hence do not pay much attention to the contract's attributes. They are also unlikely to already apply soil health-friendly management practices. These farmers are also more likely to be young farmers. Nevertheless, they are less sure that their farm will still be in business in the next ten years. Furthermore, they might have less experience in how to farm soil health-friendly (AES - soil health, Soil health-friendly). Class 3 farmers are older but are more likely to agree that their farms are still in business in 10 years. This could explain why the termination option is more important for them than the initial runtime of the contract. In addition, they are more likely to already apply soil health-friendly management practices.

	Class 1		Class 2		Class 3	
Class share	0.38		0.42		0.20	
Pred. prob.	0.86		0.04		0.32	
	Coef.	Std. Err.	Coef.	Std. Err.	Coef.	Std. Err.
<i>Regression to display preferences heterogeneity</i>						
Compensation of costs (%)	0.019***	(0.004)	0.025*	(0.014)	0.059***	(0.011)
Carbon credit price	0.034***	(0.007)	0.069*	(0.036)	0.053**	(0.023)
Contract duration	-0.063***	(0.012)	-0.181**	(0.079)	-0.023	(0.030)
Termination option	1.262***	(0.194)	1.029	(0.794)	2.961***	(0.704)
Support – annual training	0.941***	(0.265)	0.598	(1.013)	1.614**	(0.806)
Support– discount loans	0.347	(0.244)	0.264	(0.985)	1.625**	(0.805)
ASC	-0.843*	(0.452)	-5.759***	(2.154)	-9.593***	(2.123)
<i>Regression to explain class membership</i>						
Sand ^g	24.56	(3470.0)	24.92	(3470.0)	0.000	0.000
Grassland ^g	3.102*	(1.760)	2.055	(1.880)	0.000	0.000
Hectares	-0.007	(0.007)	0.001	(0.003)	0.000	0.000
Intensive management	-1.370	(1.618)	-0.445	(1.593)	0.000	0.000
Fulltime	-27.049	(510.7)	-26.36	(510.7)	0.000	0.000
AES – soil health	-2.008	(1.766)	-3.418*	(1.909)	0.000	0.000
Soil health-friendly	-5.220**	(2.363)	-6.186***	(2.377)	0.000	0.000
Share rented farmland	-0.046*	(0.025)	-0.035	(0.025)	0.000	0.000
Year of birth	0.097**	(0.049)	0.125**	(0.051)	0.000	0.000
Higher education	2.333*	(1.298)	2.104	(1.343)	0.000	0.000
Succession	-2.463	(1.672)	-3.627**	(1.726)	0.000	0.000
Statement - Climate	0.910	(0.744)	0.794	(0.783)	0.000	0.000
Statement - Productivity	2.526**	(1.214)	2.551**	(1.237)	0.000	0.000
Statement - Risk	1.131*	(0.601)	1.015	(0.629)	0.000	0.000
Constant	-176.6	(497.3)	-231.3	(496.8)	0.000	0.000
Observations	1,995					
BIC-value	953.710					
Pseudo-R²	0.433					

Table 3.2.4. Latent class model estimated to reveal preference heterogeneity within the sample.

Standard errors in parentheses * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

3.2.5.4 Strength of the effects

Table 3.2.5 holds the estimated WTA values for both models. They were calculated twice, once carbon credit price was used as the monetary variable, and once compensation of costs. When carbon credit prices increase by one Euro, farmers in the mixed logit model would give up almost 0.77 % of the cost share. For an increase of the cost share by 1 % they would accept a one Euro lower carbon credit price. For the termination option, farmers across all models and classes indicate that they are willing to accept substantially lower carbon credit prices or compensations of costs.

Finally, the predicted probabilities were calculated for carbon farming contracts that did not include additional incentives. These contracts had a duration of 20 years, offered a carbon credit price of € 30 per ton, did not include additional support for sustainable soil management, no termination option for successors, and no fixed compensation of costs. For such a contract the predicted probability in the mixed logit model is 12 % only. In the latent classes, it decreases to 60 % for the first class and is close to zero for the other two classes. This preference for fixed payments is not detectable by evaluating the WTA values.

Table 3.2.5. Estimated WTA values of the mixed logit and the LCM. Values for in-significant attributes are replaced by an x.

	Price variable - Compensation of costs (%)			
	MXL	LCM – Class 1	LCM – Class 2	LCM – Class 3
Compensation of costs (%)				
Carbon credit price	-1.077 (-1.631; -0.523)	-1.758 (-2.627; -0.889)	-2.774 (-5.606; 0.058)	-0.900 (-1.563; -0.237)
Contract duration	3.445 (2.073; 4.816)	3.251 (1.775; 4.727)	7.270 (0.016; 14.525)	x
Termination option	-53.793 (-72.033; -5.554)	-65.568 (-90.628; -40.508)	x	-50.277 (-73.415; -27.139)
Support – annual training	-30.112 (-50.141; -10.082)	-48.885 (-78.081; -19.689)	x	-27.407 (-51.547; -3.268)
Support– discount loans	-11.839 (-27.016; 3.338)	x	x	-27.583 (-51.154; -4.011)
	Price variable – Carbon Credit Price			
Compensation of costs (%)	-0.771 (-1.122; -0.420)	-0.569 (-0.850; -0.288)	-0.360 (0.728; 0.008)	-1.111 (-1.929; -0.293)
Carbon credit price				
Contract duration	2.122 (1.106; 3.139)	1.849 (0.904 ; 2.795)	2.621 (-0.122; 5.363)	x
Termination option	-45.649 (-65.508; -25.790)	-37.298 (-53.675; -20.922)	x	-55.852 (-101.910; -9.795)
Support – annual training	-26.952 (-43.525; -10.380)	-27.808 (-45.294; -10.323)	x	-30.447 (-54.769; -6.124)
Support– discount loans	-12.518 (-25.044; 0.008)	x	x	-30.641 (-54.380; -6.902)

WTA was calculated for models, where the price variable is considered fixed and not randomly distributed. The 95 % confidence intervals are provided in brackets.

3.2.6 Discussion & Conclusion

The predicted probability for farmers to participate in our hypothetical carbon credit trade contracts is low. A similar result is found for hypothetical German Humus programmes by Block et al. (2024), who state that this may be driven by a lack of knowledge of farmers about their on-farm soil organic carbon content. The findings of a lack of interest among farmers contrasts with early newspaper articles on the topic that reported on private initiatives, e.g. from farmer associations, who started to work enthusiastically on carbon farming projects (LTO Noord, 2023; Smit, 2022). The negative overall evaluation of our contracts may not only result from the limited amount of expected carbon storage. An alternative explanation is that Dutch farmers' associations initially expected that carbon credits could be generated by implementing measures that are already required when receiving CAP payments (e.g., cover crops, and buffers between arable land and rivers) (Bartolini et al., 2024). Our experiment informed farmers on the requirement of additionality, and hence the inability to generate a carbon credit without measures that go beyond CAP requirements.

The finding that the to-be-expected payments are of importance is also described by Aslam et al. (2017), who offered a fixed compensation for measures. They claimed that carbon credit trade might offer sufficient compensation by comparing WTA and carbon credit prices. However, Aslam et al. (2017) do not account for the role played by risk when looking at carbon markets. Carbon credit certification will lead to result-based payments. In the mixed logit model and the LCM, farmers value the fixed cost shares, indicating that hybrid schemes (that are only partly result-based) can be effective to promote the uptake of contracts. That farmers value fixed payments is found also in the literature on carbon farming contracts (Aslam et al., 2017), and soil health-friendly AES (Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010; Canales et al., 2024; Lapierre et al., 2023; Niskanen et al., 2021). Besides this, an important finding is that the option to terminate contracts when the farm is passed on to successors is positively perceived. The attribute was added because farmers in (Rochecouste et al., 2017) highlighted that they don't want to limit the flexibility of their children when taking over the farm.

The last attribute is 'Support for sustainable soil management', because training and education opportunities are often found to be effective (Schaub et al., 2023). The requirement to pre-finance the measures (e.g., when investing in new machinery) is described as a hindrance by Kragt et al. (2017). That cheaper loans were valued is of interest for initiatives set up by banks such as the Dutch Rabobank (Rabobank, 2022). Including such an incentive allows them to increase participation rates – even though they might be of interest to a relatively small group of farmers (class 3).

Overall, it seems that farmers will evaluate 'basic' carbon farming contracts negatively if they aim at fulfilling the quality criteria of the CRCF regulation, and do not offer additional incentives (e.g., termination options, a fixed compensation of costs, or

support for sustainable management). Such ‘basic’ contracts might be available through parties that are interested in an implementation of the system with limited interactions with other partners in the supply chain, or when farmers contract directly with a buyer. Implementing carbon farming through intermediaries (e.g. farmer associations or banks) that offer private contracts to farmers allows to include the other contract elements that hold potential because private contracts offer more flexibility (Runge et al., 2022). Larger scale implementation by intermediaries might also make it easier to fulfil the quality criteria when ‘basic’ contracts are set up between the intermediary and the buyer only. Quantification is described to be costly (Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Tiusanen et al., 2022) and private initiatives might benefit from scale effects when monitoring multiple members (Tiusanen et al., 2022). It might also be easier for them to implement additional measures more cost-effectively by offering machines to interested members. They could also ensure reliable, long-term storage more easily by having larger areas under contract than necessary as a buffer. These will be necessary when leakage occurs or when successors terminate contracts. Furthermore, a well-connected intermediate partner (e.g., a bank) might have fewer difficulties in building connections, for instance, with a more sustainability-oriented buyer willing to pay a top-up for a carbon credit providing side-effects that are beneficial for sustainability. Finally, a word of caution is necessary, changing farm practices on arable land is not the most preferred technique by the EU to achieve carbon removals, due to the risks of leakage and uncertainties regarding the removal potential (Günther et al., 2024; Paul et al., 2023).

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3.3 Germany (TUM)

3.3.1 Synthesis of the results

Title: German Farmers' Acceptance of Carbon Farming Contracts

Authors: Carina Ober, Fabian Frick

Structured Abstract: **Introduction:** While carbon farming initiatives are seen positively by many farmers, contract design is key to foster farmer participation. Thus, our research objective was to overcome participation barriers and find ways to increase farmers' acceptance of carbon farming contracts. **Methodology:** We conducted a discrete choice experiment with farmers in Germany to elicit preferences for carbon farming contract attributes. A latent class analysis identified distinct groups of farmers, based on carbon farming preferences and farm characteristics. **Results and Discussion:** Inflexible contracts with long duration and without guaranteed cost recovery proved to be not promising, as they are mostly rejected by farmers. Contracts should be more flexible but also more reliable. Farmers should have the option to terminate contracts when handing over to a successor. In addition, ancillary investment subsidies or free advice can increase the willingness to participate, especially for farmers who have not yet invested much in soil health. Considering the fluctuating price of carbon credits, a guarantee for farmers that costs of the carbon farming practices are covered is particularly relevant.

Key Words: carbon farming, carbon credits, farmer acceptance, discrete choice experiment, soil health

Case study: CO₂-Land

Incentives tested: payments for carbon credits, fixed cost shares, termination options for successors, annual training, or discounts on investments

Policy considered: EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU/2024/3012)

3.3.2 Introduction

The Regulation (EU) 2024/3012, adopted on 27 November 2024, establishes the European Union's first certification framework for permanent carbon removals, carbon farming, and carbon storage in products. This voluntary framework aims to enhance the credibility and transparency of carbon removal activities within the EU, supporting its climate neutrality objectives by 2050. One of the main categories the regulation covers is Carbon Farming. In Carbon Farming, land management practices that enhance carbon sequestration in soils are rewarded based on the amount of sequestered carbon. Common practices are reforestation, peatland restoration, improved fertilizer use, diverse crop rotations, or reduced tillage (Block et al. 2024;

McDonald et al. 2021). To be certified under the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Regulation, activities must meet four core quality criteria. First, they must demonstrate clear and measurable benefits through accurate quantification of carbon removals or soil emission reductions. Second, they need to show additionality by going beyond existing legal requirements and standard practices. Third, certified activities must ensure the long-term storage of carbon, with safeguards in place to minimize the risk of reversal. Lastly, all activities must adhere to sustainability principles, ensuring they do not cause significant harm to the environment and that they contribute positively to broader goals such as biodiversity and soil health.

As the participation of farmers in carbon farming initiatives is voluntary, farmers' acceptance of these initiatives is essential for their success. Figueredos' (2024) review of research on farmers' perspectives and attitudes towards carbon farming shows an overall positive attitude of farmers about carbon farming initiatives in multiple studies. While the basic attitude of farmers is often positive, there are still barriers that prevent farmers from actually participating in carbon farming initiatives. These obstacles range from administrative and legal challenges to practical difficulties in implementing new practices. Uncertainty around the impact of carbon farming on productivity and profitability, coupled with fluctuating carbon prices, also discourages involvement (Han and Niles 2023; Dumbrell et al. 2016; Kragt et al. 2016). High upfront investment costs and the need for significant changes in farm management further complicate adoption (Dumbrell et al. 2016).

Despite these challenges, many farmers recognize the added value of carbon farming through co-benefits such as improved soil quality and reduced erosion, often cited as the most compelling incentives (Dumbrell et al. 2016; Wang et al. 2023). Providing clear information about these advantages can significantly boost willingness to participate (Dumbrell et al. 2016).

However, carbon farming initiatives are frequently associated with substantial transaction costs, complex bureaucratic processes, and high opportunity costs (Latawiec et al. 2019; Raina et al. 2024). Long-term contractual commitments, which can severely limit land-use flexibility, pose yet another barrier, especially in cases where land is rented, making participation unfeasible (Figueredo 2024; Potthoff and Dramstad 2023).

In summary, the main obstacles farmers face include uncertain price developments that fail to guarantee cost recovery, high upfront investment costs, and long-term commitments that limit flexibility in farm management. Additionally, a lack of awareness about the on-farm benefits of carbon farming practices often hinders participation. This study aims to build on existing knowledge about these barriers by exploring the acceptance of business models designed to address and overcome them.

3.3.3 Methodology

3.3.3.1 Attribute selection, design, and implementation of the DCE

To determine farmers' preferences regarding the design of different carbon farming alternatives, we conducted a DCE with German farmers. The online data collection was conducted by a commercial farmer panel provider and took place in May 2025. 315 farmers took part in the survey.

At the beginning of the survey, general characteristics of the participating farms were collected. These included, for example, information on acreage, production priorities, or the commercial character. In addition, questions relevant to carbon sequestration were asked, such as soil type or which soil organic carbon-promoting practices are already being carried out. This was followed by the DCE, in which farmers were presented choice cards to choose one of two carbon farming initiatives, or not to choose a program at all (opt-out option). After a brief assessment of the attribute attendance, the farmers were lastly asked to answer socio-demographic questions.

The choice cards consisted of two contract options and the possibility of not choosing either option, which means staying in the status quo. The contract options were composed of 5 attributes with two to six attribute levels (see Table 3.3.1). Using a D-efficient design, 18 choice cards were created and divided into three blocks. Thus, each farmer had to answer six choice cards.

Table 3.3.1 Attributes chosen for the discrete choice experiment.

Attribute	Levels ^a
Contract duration	0 , 10, 20, 30
Termination option (for successors)	No , Yes
Support for sustainable soil management	None , Free training, 20% of one-time investment costs
Compensation of costs (%)	0% , 25%, 50%, 75%, 100%
Carbon credit price (€)	0€ , 10€, 30€, 50€, 70€, 90€, 110€

^aThe levels used for the none-option are in bold. For carbon credit prices and contract durations the none-option levels are only expressed in the third alternative (no contract).

In the following, we will go into more detail about the five attributes:

- Contract duration: In the regulation (EU/2024/3012), a quality criterion to be certified under this framework is long-term storage. The Commitment Duration attribute has the attribute levels of 10, 20, or 30 years.
- Termination option: Acceptance studies show that farmers tend to reject long-term contracts because they restrict farm management in the long term. Therefore, this attribute offers the possibility of exiting long-term obligations when the business is handed over to a successor.
- Support for sustainable soil management: Previous studies have shown that farmers are often unaware of the benefits of carbon farming initiatives and the impact on farm productivity. Support by providing free training or advice could therefore boost farmer participation. Furthermore, farmers have indicated in the past that some practices require high investment costs (e.g., no-till machines). The second attribute level offers the possibility of a one-time payment, which covers 20% of the investment in soil-friendly farming machinery. Farmers in Germany are familiar with this kind of subsidy scheme because investment subsidies are a typical form of public support (e.g., in recent years subsidies for machines for ground-level slurry application were popular).
- Compensation of costs: Soil organic carbon-promoting practices can incur additional costs (e.g., seeds for a catch crop). One risk for farmers is the uncertain price for a CO₂ certificate on the carbon market. Due to fluctuating prices, farmers cannot rely on a secure profit, and it is uncertain whether the additional costs will be recovered. This attribute indicates what percentage of the ongoing additional costs are covered when participating in this program. This cost coverage is an additional payment in addition to the carbon credit payment for the CO₂ certificate.
- Carbon credit price: The attribute shows the current price per ton of CO₂. The price is given in euros per tonne of CO₂ that could be stored.

3.3.3.2 Model estimation

To analyse the results of the discrete choice experiment, we initially estimated a conditional logit model, grounded in Random Utility Theory (RUT). According to RUT, each alternative has an associated utility composed of observable and unobservable components. The conditional logit model estimates the probability of an alternative being chosen based on its attributes, under the assumption that all respondents evaluate these attributes similarly. A key assumption of this model is the Independence of Irrelevant Alternatives (IIA), which implies that the relative odds of choosing between two options are unaffected by the presence of a third.

To test the validity of the IIA assumption, we employed the Hausman test. The test yielded statistically significant results, indicating a violation of the IIA assumption and suggesting the presence of heterogeneous preferences in the sample. Consequently, we proceeded to estimate a mixed logit model, which relaxes the IIA restriction and allows for random variation in preference parameters across individuals. This model accounts for unobserved heterogeneity and captures more realistic choice behaviour.

Given that participants in our experiment had the option to opt out of carbon farming programs, we included an alternative-specific constant (ASC) to represent the status quo. The ASC takes the value of 1 when the status quo is chosen. A positive coefficient for the ASC indicates a preference for maintaining the current situation rather than adopting a carbon farming scheme.

Recognizing that not all individuals value attributes in the same way, we conducted a Latent Class Analysis (LCA) to further explore preference heterogeneity. LCA is a segmentation technique that identifies unobserved subgroups within the sample based on similar choice behaviours. Each latent class represents a group of respondents with relatively homogeneous preferences, while preferences differ substantially between classes. The model estimates attribute-level preference parameters for each class and the probability that a respondent belongs to a given class. This approach provides valuable insights into the diversity of decision-making patterns and helps to explain why different groups make different choices.

3.3.4 Results

3.3.4.1 Descriptive statistics

The average farm size among the 315 participating farms is approximately 131 hectares, which is significantly above the national average in Germany. While the average area of permanent grassland at around 23 hectares, aligns closely with the national mean, the average arable land area in the sample is substantially larger. The sample is representative in terms of the proportion of organic farms. Compared to the national average, farms in the sample have a higher share of rented land and a greater prevalence of full-time farms. Approximately 22.2% of the farms are exclusively arable farmers with no grassland, while 7.6% manage only permanent grassland.

Table 3.3.2 Descriptive statistics of the analysed sample

Variables	Sample	Germany	Description
Average farm size (ha)	131.4	66 ^a	Total farm area in hectares

Average arable area (ha)	115.1	45.8 ^b	Arable land in hectares
Average Grassland area (ha)	23.3	21.5 ^e	Grassland in hectares
Share of rented land (%)	32.8	59 ^e	Share of rented farmland
Part-time farms (%)	39.7	47.2 ^c	Share of part-time farms
Organic farms (%)	10.5	11.4 ^d	Share of organic farms
Pure grassland farms (%)	7.6		Share of farms with only grassland
Pure arable farms (%)	22.2		Share of farms with only arable land
Predominant Soil Type (%)			
Sand	27.3		Predominant soil type is sand
Silt	11.1		Predominant soil type is silt
Clay	7.9		Predominant soil type is clay
Loam	44.8		Predominant soil type is loam
Peat	0.32		Predominant soil type is peat
Intensive (%)	68.2		Share of farms with intensive crops (sugar beet, potato, mais)
AECS soil health (%)	26.6		Participation in AECS for soil health
Age by classes (%)			

<55 years	48.3	61 ⁱ	Farmers younger than 55 years
>=55 years	51.7	39 ⁱ	Farmers older than 55 years
Agricultural education (%)	80.6	85 ⁱ	Share of farmers with agricultural training
Higher education	50.2		Share of farmers with higher education ("Hochschulreife")
Successor (%)	36.2		Farm will be transferred to a successor within the next 10 years
Statement – Climate	3.5		Farmer's level of agreement with 'Climate change impacts my farm negatively'
Statement - Productivity	4.5		Farmer's level of agreement with 'Soil health is important for my farm's productivity'
Statement – Risk	2.9		Farmer's level of agreement with 'To achieve profit maximisation - I am more willing to take risks than others'

- a) BMEL-Statistik: Betriebsstruktur und Entwicklung landwirtschaftlicher Betriebe
- b) BMEL-Statistik: Bodennutzung in Deutschland
- c) Studie zum Nebenerwerb in der Landwirtschaft: So ist die Lage - Bauernzeitung
- d) BMEL-Statistik: Ökologischer Landbau
- e) Agrarstrukturerhebung (statistisches Bundesamt) 2023

The predominant soil type is loam, and nearly 30% of the farm managers reported participating in Agri-Environmental and Climate Schemes (AECS) aimed at improving soil health. Most participants agree with the statement that soil health is crucial for productivity, and also the view that climate change has a negative impact on production is widely accepted.

Roughly one-third of the farms are expected to be transferred to a successor within the next 10 years. Farm managers in the sample tend to be older than the national average, while the share of those with formal agricultural training is in line with the national average.

3.3.4.2 Results from the Mixed Logit Estimation

Table 3.3.3 presents the estimation results for the mixed logit model with random effects for all contract attributes. These model specifications best fit the data according to the AIC and BIC criteria.

Table 3.2.3 Mixed logit model to explain farmer's decision for a carbon farming contract.

	Coef.	SD. Error	S.D.	SD. Error	WTA
<i>Contract attributes</i>					
Contract duration	-0.158***	(0.013)	0.115***	(0.010)	8.91
Termination option	1.035***	(0.138)	1.375***	(0.158)	-72.97
Support - free training	0.405**	(0.157)	0.733***	(0.236)	-19.89
Support - investment	0.705***	(0.152)	-0.049	(0.249)	-38.79
Compensation of costs	1.996***	(0.233)	-1.616***	(0.313)	-129.93
Carbon credit price	0.017***	(0.002)	-0.020***	(0.003)	
ASC	2.742***	(0.512)	-0.256	(0.259)	-95.22
<i>Interaction effects</i>					
ASC * sand	-0.172	(0.365)	-0.274	(0.4529)	
ASC * grassland	-0.010**	(0.005)	0.012***	0.004	
ASC * Total land	-0.001	(0.001)	0.010***	(0.001)	
ASC * intensive	-0.366	(0.356)	0.734***	(0.239)	
ASC * parttime	0.534	(0.248)	-3.310***	(0.465)	
ASC * AECS	-0.229	(0.387)	0.244	(0.344)	
ASC * Share rented land	-0.255	(0.247)	-0.325	(0.434)	
ASC * Higher education	-0.398	(0.354)	-1.775***	(0.289)	

ASC * Successor	-0.087	(0.303)	0.041	(0.409)
ASC * Climate	-0.509*	(0.303)	0.813*	(0.317)
Observations	5,652			

* p<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

The contract duration shows a significant negative effect. Farmers, therefore, reject long-term commitments. The option of being able to terminate the contract upon handover to a successor significantly increases the utility and thus the willingness to participate. The option of free advice increases the utility of carbon farming programs. The coverage of 20% of the acquisition costs of one-off investments also has a positive effect on the willingness to participate, as it increases the utility of the program. The greater the proportion of ongoing costs covered, the greater the willingness to participate. As expected, the higher the price for the carbon certificate, the higher the likelihood of participation. Farmers in general show a significant preference for the status quo, and the predicted probability for choosing the status quo option is 54%.

In addition to contract attributes, we also investigated how farm characteristics influence participation in carbon credit programs. While most farm characteristics do not have a significant effect on the willingness to deviate from the status quo, the interactions of the ASC with pure grassland farms and the climate change statement do have a significant effect. Farmers with pure grassland farms prefer to remain in the status quo and not participate in carbon credit programs, while farmers who expect negative impacts of climate change are more likely to participate in carbon credit programs.

The WTA shows that a payment of around €90 is necessary for farmers to participate in a carbon farming initiative. The necessary payment is increased by long-term contracts, while cost recovery, investment support and advice reduce it.

3.3.4.3 Results from the Latent Class Model

We included the AIC and BIC, but also subjective criteria in the determination of the factor number. While the BIC suggests a 5-class solution, only very small differences between the classes were found here with only five contract attributes. Clear classes could not be defined. We therefore opted for a three-class solution.

Farmers in classes 1 and 2 show a basic willingness to participate in carbon credit programs. They differ significantly from each other only in terms of investment costs. For farmers in class 1, the coverage of 20% of acquisition costs is significantly positive, while this option has no significant meaning for farmers in class 2. Differences in farm characteristics are a likely reason for this.

Class 3 differs very clearly from classes 1 and 2. While farmers in classes 1 and 2 are in general willing to participate in carbon credit programs, farmers in class 3 prefer to stay in the status quo option. Therefore, less contract attributes are decisive for participation. While farmers 1 and 2 are significantly influenced by the termination option, this does not appear to be important for farmers in class 3. The price of the carbon certificate is also not decisive for farmers in class 3.

Compared to class 3, farmers in classes 1 and 2 are characterized by the fact that they are more likely to expect negative effects of climate change while also having a higher level of education. Farmers in class 1 tend to be younger, while farmers in class 2 pursue a more intensive production strategy.

Table 3.3.4 Latent class model estimation to reveal preference heterogeneity within the sample

	Class 1		Class 2		Class 3	
Class share	0.441		0.234		0.324	
	Coef.	Std. Err.	Coef.	Std. Err.	Coef.	Std. Err.
<i>Regression to display preferences heterogeneity</i>						
Contract duration	-0.044***	0.006	-0.402***	0.050	-0.072**	0.034
Termination option	0.720***	0.092	2.499***	0.453	0.783	0.500
Support - free training	0.126	0.120	0.533	0.532	1.258	.
Support - investment	0.275**	0.120	-0.378	0.415	1.686***	0.398
Compensation of costs	1.207***	0.665	2.800***	0.631	1.611**	0.730
Carbon credit price	0.009***	0.002	0.040***	0.007	-0.003	0.008
ASC	0.046	0.223	0.412	0.535	4.502***	0.740
<i>Regression to explain class membership</i>						
Sand	0.048	0.323	-0.259	0.411	0.000	0.000
Grassland	0.004	0.003	-.003	.	0.000	0.000
Total land	-0.0003	0.0007	-0.002	0.001	0.000	0.000
Intensive management	0.193	0.305	0.720*	0.392	0.000	0.000

Fulltime	0.298	0.314	0.158	0.390	0.000	0.000
AECS – soil health	0.280	0.335	0.319	0.407	0.000	0.000
Share rented farmland	0.135	0.213	0.083	0.343	0.000	0.000
Year of birth	-0.022**	0.010	-0.009	0.012	0.000	0.000
Higher education	0.490*	0.290	0.590*	0.352	0.000	0.000
Succession	0.470	0.321	-0.096	0.406	0.000	0.000
Statement - Climate	0.230*	0.130	0.318**	0.158	0.000	0.000
Statement - Productivity	0.207	0.145	0.310	0.200	0.000	0.000
Statement - Risk	0.163	0.132	0.183	0.163	0.000	0.000
Constant	-1.561*	0.802	-3.654***	1.130	0.000	0.000
Observations	5,670					
BIC-value	2605.5192					

3.3.5. Discussion and Conclusion

Using a DCE, we assessed farmers' preferences regarding the design of carbon credit programs. The goal was to address previously identified barriers through alternative program designs within the framework of EU Regulation (EU/2024/3012) in order to explore ways to increase acceptance among farmers.

Using a mixed logit model, we analysed preferences for five contract attributes as well as their interaction with farm characteristics. Previous studies (e.g., Figueredo, 2024; Potthoff and Dramstad, 2023) have shown that farmers are particularly reluctant to commit to long-term management strategies. Long-term contracts limit flexibility in land use, and participation is often not possible when land is leased. Additionally, farmers who are planning to hand over their farm to a successor often avoid entering into obligations that might affect the next generation (Ober et al. 2025). Our study confirms this finding: the longer the contract duration, the lower the willingness to participate.

However, long-term commitment to soil-friendly management is crucial for the climate benefit of such measures. Practices that promote soil organic matter can sequester carbon in the soil, whereas intensive land use may lead to CO₂ emissions back into the atmosphere (McDonald et al. 2021). For this reason, long-term management is one of the core quality criteria in the EU regulation. To address farmers' concerns and encourage participation, we included in our choice experiment an option that allows obligations related to carbon credit generation to be terminated if the farm is transferred to a successor. This option has a positive effect on willingness to participate and should be considered in future contract designs.

Another issue highlighted in previous literature is that farmers often struggle to assess the impact of carbon farming on productivity and profitability (Dumbrell et al. 2016; Han and Niles 2023; Kragt et al. 2016). This uncertainty could potentially be mitigated by making relevant information more accessible (Dumbrell et al. 2016). Our results show that offering free advisory services has a significant positive effect on participation. That said, our analysis only captures the effect of offering such advice, not the effect of the advice itself. If, for instance, farmers get to know more about carbon farming and its positive effects on soil health during their training, this might further increase participation. Future studies could investigate whether farmers' knowledge about carbon farming has a positive impact on their willingness to participate.

Another barrier to farmers' willingness to participate in carbon credit programs are the potentially high investment costs involved (Dumbrell et al. 2016). These costs may include, for example, the purchase of new equipment for no-till farming. In addition, ongoing expenses, such as for specialized seeds or mechanical weed control, can be substantial. Since carbon credit prices fluctuate, farmers cannot reliably calculate cost recovery, which adds to the uncertainty. To address this issue, our experiment tested two compensation mechanisms: First, a 20% subsidy on the purchase of new machinery, and second, partial reimbursement of ongoing operational costs. Both measures had a statistically significant positive effect on

farmers' willingness to participate. Additionally, higher carbon credit prices were also associated with increased participation.

A literature review by Figueredo (2024) has previously shown that farmers are generally open to carbon credit programs. Our mixed logit model does not support this result: opting to remain in the status quo, i.e., not participating in such programs, provides significantly greater utility for farmers, on average. A payment of nearly 100€ would be necessary to get farmers to participate.

However, farm characteristics do influence participation. Farmers operating on pure grassland farms are less likely to take part in carbon credit programs. This may be because targeted increasing of soil organic matter is generally more difficult in grassland cultivation. On the other hand, farmers who believe in the negative impacts of climate change are more likely to participate in carbon credit programs. These programs may be seen as a strategy to adapt to changing production conditions and as a risk management strategy for increasing production risk due to more frequent weather extremes.

Following the mixed logit analysis, we conducted a latent class analysis to explore heterogeneity in farmers' preferences. This analysis revealed three distinct farmer classes.

Class 1, comprising about 44% of respondents, is the largest. Like class 2, they show a general willingness to participate in carbon credit programs. Farmers in this group tend to be younger compared to the other two classes. Therefore, they respond particularly positively to subsidies for initial investments, which may help young farmers to adapt farm management to their personal preferences.

Class 2, accounting for 23% of farmers, is oftentimes engaged in more intensive practices. They demonstrate a high willingness to participate, provided the programs offer sufficient cost coverage and include an exit option from long-term contracts. Coverage of investment costs seems to be less decisive, as maybe due to already intensive management, they are already well positioned in terms of their machines.

Class 3 includes 32% of the respondents and in contrast to classes 1 and 2 shows a low willingness to participate overall. These farmers tend to be less educated and do not expect negative impacts from climate change, both of which likely reduce their interest in joining such programs.

Our findings indicate that a substantial segment of farmers (Class 1 and 2) is considering sustainable land management and is open to participating if certain conditions are met. These are the option to terminate contracts when giving the farm to a successor and a high cost compensation. Class 1 can be additionally encouraged to participate through financial support for investments. Farmers who are sceptical of climate change and less educated (Class 3) are significantly less likely to participate.

In summary, strict contract models, such as those with long durations, are not conducive to high acceptance of carbon farming practices among the farmers in our sample. When contracts are designed more flexibly, for instance by offering an exit option, or by providing financial support for initial investments, they can attract farmers' interest. However, it is important to keep in mind that one of the core criteria of EU Regulation (EU/2024/3012) is the additionality of measures. Practices that are already funded by other programs, such as agri-environmental and climate schemes (AECS), for example, cannot be additionally financed by carbon farming initiatives. With the new CAP funding period starting in 2023, farmers in Germany have many opportunities to receive support for soil health-promoting practices through both the first and second pillars of the CAP. For example, eco-schemes under Pillar I support agroforestry systems or extensive grassland management. AECS under Pillar II promote humus-enhancing crop rotations, the avoidance of intensive crops, or conservation tillage methods. Farmers often view AECS as a reliable source of funding, while carbon credit programs are perceived as risky (Figueredo 2024). Introducing guaranteed cost coverage into carbon credit programs could make them more attractive. However, to make definitive conclusions about farmer preferences, more studies are needed in which farmers directly choose between these two types of support programs.

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3.4 Germany (ZALF)

3.4.1 Synthesis of the results

Title: The supply of biodiversity and ecosystem services credits: what matters to farmers in Germany

Authors: Ferdinand Lang, Cheng Chen, Mohammed Hussen Alemu, Thomas Lundhede, Søren Bøye Olsen, Bettina Matzdorf

Structured Abstract:

Introduction: To increase private investments into biodiversity and ecosystem services, market-based business models such as credits are increasingly being seen as a promising opportunity. In this context, the European Commission recently published its 'Roadmap towards Nature Credits', formulating initial steps to develop a regulatory framework enabling such a business case in the European Union. Particularly, farmers are envisioned to play a crucial role to supply such credits by implementing environmental measures on their land in exchange for remuneration from private investors. However, little is known about farmer preferences for participating in privately financed market-based schemes such as credits. Our study aimed at investigating farmers' willingness to participate in such credit schemes, addressing some of the entry barriers and technological opportunities currently being observed in real-world marketplaces (e.g., online marketplaces). **Methodology:** We conducted a discrete choice experiment with farmers in Germany to investigate preferences for supplying biodiversity and ecosystem services credits and analysed our data specifying a random parameter logit model (or mixed logit) in willingness-to-accept-space. Moreover, as our case study we used a real-world and currently operating online marketplace for such credits: AgoraNatura. **Results and Discussion:** Our results indicate general interest of farmers to supply biodiversity and ecosystem services credits via an online marketplace. In addition, we observe that public seed-funding covering fixed costs for credits holds substantial value for farmers and may boost engagement by financially derisking participation. We also note that artificial intelligence-based monitoring applications are valued by farmers. Finally, our analysis shows that an online marketplace for biodiversity and ecosystem services credits is of interest to farmers and could serve as an appreciated channel to facilitate private sector investment in respective credits.

Key Words: biodiversity, ecosystem services, credits, blending, discrete choice experiment, willingness to accept

Case study: AgoraNatura

Incentives tested: remuneration for biodiversity and ecosystem services credits, public funding for fixed costs of credits, artificial intelligence-based monitoring technologies, independent vs monitoring through service provider

Policy considered: Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, EU Soil Strategy for 2030, EU Roadmap towards nature credits

3.4.2 Introduction

Aiming to incentivise increased private investment into nature conservation, the European Commission has recently presented its 'Roadmap towards Nature Credits', formulating initial steps to develop a regulatory framework that is able to support scalable business models for biodiversity and ecosystem service (ES) credits (European Commission, 2025). For the supply of such credits, farmers are anticipated to play a pivotal role. However, the extent to which farmers are open to participating in such privately financed and voluntary business models remains insufficiently understood.

Analysing farmer preferences for biodiversity and ES credits is different to preferences for publicly funded agri-environmental and climate measures (AECMs). Arguably one of the main differences is that AECMs generally offer somewhat guaranteed compensation for opportunity costs (such as foregone economic revenue) (Kuhfuss et al., 2016), while market-based schemes carry risks for farmers such as demand uncertainty for credits (European Commission, 2025; zu Ermgassen et al., 2025). Consequently, farmers face the risk that initial investments made to supply such credits (e.g., expenses for credit development and certification) may turn into sunk costs. Such a risk presents an entry barrier to farmers wanting to participate in credit schemes. To overcome this barrier, blended finance – which combines public funds with private capital – has previously been discussed as a promising opportunity to de-risk participation and leverage stakeholder engagement (Reed et al., 2022; den Heijer & Coppens, 2023). Public funding, for instance, could help reduce risk by covering initial fixed costs related to the conceptualisation and certification of credits (see also European Commission, 2025; Flammer et al., 2025; Rode et al., 2019). On the other hand, revenue made through the selling of credits can remunerate farmers for forgone production income or even generate profits. Although the strategic value of blended finance in mobilising private capital for conservation efforts has been previously recognised (Havemann et al., 2020; Reed et al., 2022; UNEP, 2023; Seidl et al., 2024; zu Ermgassen et al., 2025), its specific influence on farmer engagement within biodiversity and ES credit markets remains insufficiently studied. This represents a timely research gap with direct relevance for current policy initiatives.

Another crucial aspect in the context of increasing private investment for biodiversity and ES credits is that investors often hesitate to invest into such markets due to concerns about reputational risks (e.g., the fear of being associated with greenwashing (Chen et al., 2024; Krause & Matzdorf, 2019; zu Ermgassen et al., 2025). Enhancing the integrity and demonstrable impact of biodiversity and ES credits is therefore essential, and robust and transparent monitoring standards will play a central role to attract more investment. Recent innovations in artificial intelligence (AI) applications, especially machine learning (ML), offer promising tools to address this challenge. ML technology applied to visual and acoustic data collected from agricultural landscapes have shown considerable promise for monitoring biodiversity and ES outcomes (Alotaibi & Nassif, 2024; Andermann et al., 2022; IEEP, 2024; Norouzzadeh et al., 2018; Reynolds et al., 2024; Wäldchen & Mäder, 2018). Furthermore, such automated monitoring technology can also substantially lower the costs associated with monitoring (IEEP, 2024; Norouzzadeh et al., 2018)

and reduce administrative burdens (IEEP, 2024; Hannus et al., 2020). However, widespread adoption hinges on farmers' acceptance of these technologies. To date, no research has examined European farmers' preferences regarding the use of AI-based monitoring in the context of biodiversity and ES credit schemes. Importantly, deploying such technologies on farms may raise new concerns, particularly around data privacy and autonomy. An important question, therefore, is whether farmers would prefer to manage AI-based monitoring themselves or delegate this responsibility to service providers.

In summary, this study aims to investigate the supply side of biodiversity and ES credits and what preferences farmers have towards mechanisms and opportunities seen to provide promising pathways for the scalability of such business models.

3.4.3 Methodology

To assess farmer preferences for biodiversity and ES credits, characterised by blended finance and AI-based monitoring opportunities we conducted a DCE. Our survey was distributed in April 2025 to farmers across Germany managing arable land. Overall, 301 farmers completed the survey. Descriptive statistics of our sample are provided in Table 3.4.1 .

Table 3.4.1: Descriptive statistics of the analysed sample

Variables	Sample
Age	Mean: 52.4
Gender (%):	Female: 8.64% Male: 91.36% Diverse: 0%
Ownership of managed land (%):	Leases most of managed land: 40.5% Owns most of land: 54.5% Neither owns nor leases managed land but makes land use and investment decisions: 5%
Size of managed land (ha):	Less than 1: 1.33% 1-10: 1.33% 10-100: 62.13% 100-500: 23.26% More than 500: 0.66%

German federal state where largest share of farmland is located (%):	
Baden-Württemberg	9.30%
Bavaria	52.16%
Berlin	0%
Brandenburg	1%
Bremen	0%
Hamburg	0%
Hesse	6.31%
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	1.33%
Lower Saxony	18.60%
North Rhine-Westphalia	4.32%
Rhineland-Palatinate	2.33%
Saarland	0.33%
Saxony	1.33%
Saxony-Anhalt	1.66%
Schleswig-Holstein	1%
Thuringia	0.33%

In our DCE we framed biodiversity and ES credits representing flower strip measures on arable land with a duration of five years. We chose a commonly known and general reference scenario to provide farmers with a common starting ground before answering our choice scenarios and to ensure comparability of results. Farmers were informed these flower strip measures would generate credits which they could offer to investors via the online marketplace AgoraNatura. In total farmers were asked to answer six choice scenarios. Each time they were able to choose among two individual flower strip measures and one opt-out alternative. The two individual flower strip measure alternatives were characterised by four varying attributes (a more detailed description can be found in Table 3.4.2):

1. Public funding for fixed costs (0% to 100%);
2. Monitoring type (farmer-led vs service provider);
3. Monitoring technique (manual vs automated monitoring);
4. Remuneration (ha/year) (€500 to €2,500).

The funding attribute reflected the blended finance mechanism mentioned in the introduction, where public support was intended to derisk of up-front investment

for developing and certifying credits. For simplification – and based on expert input – we told farmers to assume fixed costs €1,000 for a five-year flower strip project. The goal was to explore whether public funding for fixed costs could stimulate farmer participation for otherwise market-based and privately financed (or remunerated) biodiversity and ES credits.

Monitoring techniques were inspired by currently applied techniques on AgoraNatura and emerging AI-based monitoring applications. Manual monitoring was framed as traditional species observation, while automated monitoring was framed as automatically uploaded and processed image, video or acoustic data obtained via drones or smartphones.

Remuneration levels per credit were inspired by past AgoraNatura projects in combination with expert consultations of the marketplace.

Table 3.4.2: Attributes and levels of choice experiment.

Attribute	Levels (coding)
Funding for conceptualisation and certification costs	0% (reference) 33.33% (dummy) 66.66% (dummy) 100% (dummy)
Monitoring – type	Monitoring through service provider (reference) Independent monitoring (dummy)
Monitoring – technique	Manual monitoring (reference) Automated monitoring (dummy)
Remuneration (ha/year)	€500, €750, €1000, €1500, €2000 or €2500 (continuous)

3.4.4 Results

Below, we present the results of our random parameter logit (or mixed logit) model (RP – MXL) using the WTA-space specification (see also Hannus et al., 2020). For the final analysis we excluded a total of 9 farmers due to protest behaviours. The final sample used for analysis included 292 farmers.

3.4.4.1 Results

Funding for conceptualisation and certification costs (blending):

From our results we observe that farmers on average show a positive mean estimate for the opt-out alternative (€590/credit). This estimate represents the lowest average amount of remuneration our farmer sample would want to receive to supply credits. Among public funding levels for fixed costs, full funding (100%) is most valued (€330/credit), followed by 66.66% (€228) and 33.33% (€149). These estimates must be understood as monetary values farmers place on the respective funding levels. Thus, the results imply a strong preference for higher funding, where farmers are willing to accept less remuneration per credit when funding increases. However, we also observe significant standard deviation estimates which point to potential subgroup differences across our sample.

Monitoring alternatives:

From our results we observe an insignificant estimate for independent monitoring (€10/credit) while farmers on average significantly value automated monitoring (€180/credit). This indicates if farmers have the possibility to use automated monitoring (compared to manual monitoring), they on average are willing to forego €180 of remuneration per credit. Though, we again observe significant standard deviation estimates which point to potential subgroup differences across our sample.

3.4.5 Discussion

3.4.5.1 Willingness to Supply Biodiversity and ES Credits

As studies on farmers' willingness to offer biodiversity and ES credits via market-based approaches generally remain scarce, we perhaps compare our findings regarding general willingness to supply biodiversity and ES credits to current compensation levels of publicly funded five-year flower strip measures (i.e. AECMs). Since the majority of our sample are farmers in either Bavaria (52.16%), Lower Saxony (18.60%), Baden-Württemberg (9.30%), and Hesse (6.31%), we here focus on these regions. In Bavaria remuneration can vary between approx. €400 – €1100/ha/year (StMELF, 2025) depending on yield index, in Lower Saxony between approx. €910 – €1250/ha/year (ML, 2023), in Baden-Württemberg approx. €730/ha/year (MLR, 2024) and in Hesse approx. €750/ha/year (HMLU, 2025). Notably, the minimum remuneration our sample on average requires to receive in order to consider supplying biodiversity and ES credits (€590/credit) is less than offered remuneration by the above-mentioned federal states except for the minimum in Bavaria.

3.4.5.2 Blended Finance

Regarding the use of blended finance for biodiversity and ES credits via market-based systems, particularly applied to derisking fixed costs, no prior research appears to mirror our supply-side focus or experimental design. Nonetheless, we may compare our findings to existing literature investigating the effect of fixed costs in publicly funded AECMs which also show that lowering the financial risk of fixed costs positively affects farmer participation (Ducos et al., 2009; Espinosa-Goded et al., 2013). As we observe that farmers are willing to forego an increasing amount of remuneration per credit as respective seed-funding increases, we contribute to a timely discussion on the development of such business models

(European Commission, 2025) as well as the integration of publicly funded with private market-based schemes (Reed et al., 2022). Furthermore, we find support for our blending approach in the European Commission's recently published 'Roadmap towards Nature Credits' which also acknowledges the role of fixed costs potentially presenting a barrier to farmer participation and that participation might be enhanced through "seed finance or by de-risking mechanisms to reward and scale up early biodiversity certification and nature credits initiatives that are essential to attract private capital" (European Commission, 2025:10). Thus, we believe our results may be useful for policymakers to further develop the Roadmap towards Nature Credits.

3.4.5.3 Monitoring

The second objective of our study was to investigate farmer preferences for AI-based monitoring technologies and the responsibility on implementing them in order to substantiate biodiversity and ES credits. While technological advancements present great opportunities for monitoring environmental improvements that substantiate biodiversity and ES credits, we are not aware of any studies having examined farmers willingness to adopt such technologies. On average, we do find farmers value the opportunity to apply such technologies.

That said, our analysis is not without limits. Future work should expand our sample size to better represent German farmers – especially with farmers from East Germany, which were underrepresented. In this context, it would be especially interesting to see how public funding for fixed costs affects farmers in these regions. With larger average farm sizes in East Germany, these farms might be more flexible in managing fixed costs and thus are perhaps less risk averse. Finally, it would be interesting to replicate the study conducting a revealed preference DCE, which is more realistic in capturing farmer behaviour and to some extent is able to mitigate hypothetical bias inherent in stated preference DCEs (Hensher, 2010; Mariel et al., 2021).

3.4.6 Conclusion

This research offers empirical insight into German farmers' willingness to supply biodiversity and ES credits via an online marketplace. Moreover, we observe that public funding for fixed costs of credits (i.e. seed funding) as well as the opportunity to apply AI-based monitoring technologies may stimulate participation. However, preference heterogeneity across the sample exists. In summary, we hope our findings can contribute to recent policy initiatives driving the development of biodiversity and ES credits such as the European Commission's 'Roadmap towards Nature Credits'. Moreover, we emphasise the importance of flexible framework conditions in designing biodiversity and ES credit programmes in order to both account for varying preferences of farmers and maximise farmer participation.

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3.5 Italy

3.5.1 Synthesis of the results

Title: Italian Farmers' Acceptance of soil health Contracts

Authors: Maria Raimondo, Lucrezia Abruzzo, Riccardo Scarparo, Fabio Bartolini

Structured Abstract:

Context: Soil health is crucial in food security, biodiversity conservation, and climate change mitigation. However, in recent decades, intensive agriculture and unsustainable practices have led to significant soil degradation, negatively impacting agricultural productivity and ecosystem services. Agriculture plays a central role in the economy of Italy, in particular, the coastal area of Emilia-Romagna has a strong agricultural vocation, but nowadays faces environmental challenges that have become a growing concern in many regions, such as salinisation, subsidence, and loss of organic matter. To mitigate these issues, the European Union promotes sustainable farming practices through the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and the European Green Deal. Among these, conservative agriculture, focused on soil conservation, has emerged as a promising solution to restore soil health and biodiversity while improving water retention and carbon sequestration. **Objective:** This study aims to assess the willingness of Italian farmers to adopt sustainable practices, specifically conservation agriculture, and to explore the financial incentives that could encourage them to implement such measures. The Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) is used to evaluate the farmers' preferences for various program attributes related to sustainable farming. **Method:** The Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) used in this analysis evaluates the quality criteria within the management requirements of hypothetical programs (additionality, quantification, sustainability) and the programs' attributes, including long-term storage. **Results & Conclusion:** The study reveals that Italian farmers are generally hesitant to join soil conservation programs, especially when long-term programs involve significant income risks. Participation increases with higher per-hectare payments, while result-based payment reduces the likelihood of acceptance. Farmers require €15–78/ha in compensation to accept less favourable program terms. To improve uptake, programs should offer greater flexibility, minimise perceived risks, and align better with farmers' economic priorities and expectations.

Key Words: sustainable agriculture, conservative agriculture, farmer preferences, carbon sequestration, soil health, CAP, EU Green Deal, Discrete Choice Experiment

Case study: Italian Farmers.

Incentives tested: Payments for improving organic matter

Policy considered: AECS with area-based payments, results-based and hybrid

3.5.2 Introduction

Soils in the European Union play a fundamental role in food security, biodiversity conservation, and climate change mitigation. However, intensive land management and unsustainable practices have led to significant soil degradation in recent decades, negatively impacting agricultural productivity and ecosystem services. Areas such as the coastal zones of Emilia-Romagna face specific challenges, including organic matter loss, salinisation, and soil erosion. Adopting sustainable farming practices, such as conservation agriculture, represents an effective solution to improve soil health and enhance the resilience of agricultural systems. These practices include reduced soil tillage, cover crops, and diversified crop rotations. Despite their benefits, adoption remains limited, partly due to a lack of adequate financial incentives and farmers' perception of increased economic risk. This study analyses Italian farmers' preferences regarding adopting conservation agriculture practices, particularly assessing their willingness to accept per hectare to implement them. Additionally, it examines the main support mechanisms available at the European and national levels, highlighting current policies and economic incentives accessible to farmers.

3.5.3 Policy framework

In recent years, European policies on soil protection have evolved to address the growing challenges of soil degradation and climate change. Within this framework, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) remains the main support tool for European farmers, incorporating specific measures to promote more sustainable agricultural practices. The CAP 2023-2027 is structured around two main pillars: the first provides direct payments to farmers who comply with environmental standards, while the second supports rural development through programs that foster innovation and sustainability. These initiatives align with the broader vision of the European Green Deal and the "Farm to Fork" strategy, which seeks to make agricultural systems more sustainable by reducing pesticide and fertiliser use, expanding organic farming, and protecting soil biodiversity. At the core of these policies is the recognition of soil's crucial role in mitigating climate change, preserving its fertility, and maintaining its carbon storage capacity. Conservation agriculture plays a key role among the agricultural practices that align with these objectives. This approach focuses on improving soil health and agricultural productivity by minimising soil disturbance, promoting crop diversification, and using cover crops to protect the land. Reducing soil tillage helps maintain soil structure, decrease erosion, and limit CO₂ emissions. Meanwhile, crop rotation enhances soil fertility, prevents pest outbreaks, and improves nutrient efficiency. Cover crops further safeguard the soil from erosion, increase organic matter content, and support microbial biodiversity. Encouraging the adoption of conservation agriculture requires not only financial support but also greater awareness among farmers of the long-term benefits of these practices. The CAP offers direct payments for sustainable soil management, while rural development programs provide targeted funding for soil conservation measures. However, the

effectiveness of these incentives largely depends on how farmers perceive the costs and benefits of transitioning to these methods.

3.5.4 Methodology

3.5.4.1 Questionnaire Structure

The questionnaire submitted to Italian farmers was divided into five distinct sections, aiming to systematically and coherently explore preferences regarding the adoption of soil health-related conservation agricultural practices. The sections are described in detail below:

1. **Introductory Section: Perception about Carbon Sequestration and Regulatory Context:** This part, common to all project partners, provided basic information on carbon sequestration, potential benefits for farmers, and the basic principles of carbon credit remuneration mechanisms. It also outlined the political framework, particularly the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and European Green Deal initiatives.
2. **Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE):** The central section of the questionnaire consisted of a series of “choice cards” designed to simulate realistic program scenarios. Farmers were asked to choose between two program options (A and B), each with different characteristics, or to reject both via the “opt out” option. The aim was to investigate preferences regarding the duration of program commitment, the estimated income loss, the type and structure of payment and the amount of remuneration per hectare.
3. **Socio-demographic Section:** This section collected personal and business information from respondents, including age and education, total farm area and type of crops (arable, pasture, etc.), certifications (e.g., organic) and the presence of a potential successor.
4. **Socio-psychological Constructs:** Farmers were asked to express their level of agreement with statements about their social and personal norms (e.g., “other farmers in my area adopt sustainable practices”), their trust in European institutions, their environmental concerns, and their perception of impacts on human health.
5. **Environmental Risk Perception Section:** This section explored how farmers perceive the risks associated with soil degradation in their area. It included questions on the frequency of events such as erosion, organic matter loss, and salinisation and the perceived impact on the future of their business.

3.5.4.2 Attribute Selection and DCE Design

To design a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE), it is essential to select relevant, understandable, and realistic attributes for participants, in this case, farmers. The attributes were chosen based on scientific literature on adopting agri-environmental practices (Herzon et al., 2018; Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010). Four main attributes were considered:

Table 3.5.1: Attribute selection for the DCE

Attribute	Levels	Description
Annual payment per hectare	100 €, 200 €	Compensation for adopting conservation practices
Type of payment	100% fixed; 50% fixed + 50% result-based; 100% result-based	Payment modalities: fixed or performance-based
Estimated income reduction	Low, Medium, High	Represents perceived income loss risk
Commitment duration	5, 10, 20 years	Minimum period of practice adoption

These attributes reflect economic aspects (payment, income loss) and operational and risk-related factors (program duration, type of payment), all of which are known to influence farmers' decision-making.

Payments from €100 to €200/ha reflect realistic ranges, consistent with CAP incentives and marginal costs associated with practices such as no-till farming and cover crops. Durations from 5 to 20 years reflect the time required to obtain tangible soil benefits.

Payment types test preferences between area-based and result-based mechanisms, a key aspect in the literature, as the latter are expected to provide cost-effectiveness of the measure (D'Alberto et al., 2024; Vergamini et al., 2024)

Income reduction and administrative burdens reflect fears of economic loss, a frequent barrier to adoption (Canales et al., 2024).

Each survey participant received randomised choice cards containing two program alternatives (A and B) and a third "opt-out" option. An example is shown below:

Table 3.5.2: Example of a choice card (in Italian)

Attribute	Alternative A	Alternative B
Durata di adozione della pratica	5 anni	20 anni
Variazione (riduzione) del reddito agricolo (Reduction of agricultural income)	Basso	Alto
Pagamento per ha (Payment per ha)	€100 per ha	€200 per ha

Tipo di pagamento (Type of payment)	100% in base all'aumento della sostanza organica	50% di pagamento fisso per ha + 50% in base all'aumento della sostanza organica
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The survey was set up online on the Qualtrics platform. Data collection for the experiment began in October 2024 and ended in March 2025.

3.5.4.3 Estimation

For the estimation, a mixed logit model was estimated. The mixed logit model assumes that respondents (i) select the most attractive alternative from a set of J alternatives. The utility of choosing an alternative (U_{ij}) depends on the program's attributes and their observed levels, represented by a vector x_{ij} , and an independently distributed random term (ε_{ij}). Individual-specific coefficients β_i determine the effect of the attributes on the utility (Eq. 1):

$$U_{ij} = \beta_i x_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (1)$$

The mixed logit model assumes that estimators are continuously distributed with density $f(\beta | \theta)$, where θ represents the distribution parameters. As shown in Equation (2), the probability of choosing a program becomes an integral over β values and is determined by simulation. In the end, the coefficients display the weighted average of the participants' preferences:

$$P_{ij} = \int L_{ij}(\beta) f(\beta) d\beta \quad (2)$$

Where $L_{ij}(\beta)$ is the conditional choice probability given a specific value of the preference parameters β ; $f(\beta)$ is the probability density function of the random coefficients β , and $\int d\beta$ integrates over all possible values of β .

While the mixed logit accounts for preference heterogeneity using individual-specific coefficients, it lacks detailed information on differences in attribute perception (Train, 2009). WTA measures the substitution rate between an attribute and monetary value (Train, 2009). In models with random effects, calculating the ratio directly would lead to unreasonably high values (Train & Weeks, 2015), hence the price coefficient was considered fixed when calculating WTA for the mixed logit model.

The Willingness to Accept (WTA) is a measure used to quantify the monetary compensation that individuals require to accept a less favourable condition in a choice experiment. It is particularly useful in evaluating trade-offs between monetary and non-monetary attributes in program design. The WTA is calculated as follows (3):

$$WTA = -\beta_{attribute} / \beta_{payment} \quad (3)$$

This formula represents the negative ratio between the coefficient of a non-monetary attribute ($\beta_{attribute}$) and the coefficient of the payment attribute ($\beta_{payment}$). It indicates the amount of money (in euros per hectare) a farmer

would need as compensation to accept an unfavourable change, such as a longer program duration or a higher income reduction risk.

3.5.6 RESULTS

3.5.6.1 Descriptive Statistics

The sample includes 109 farmers from Italy. The main socio-demographic characteristics are reported in the table below.

Table 3.5.3: Descriptive statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Description
Age	53 years	11.7	Average age
Farm size	42.5 ha	28.3	Total area under management
Organic farming	18%	–	Certification
Presence of a successor	64%	–	Active or expected family successor
Higher education	35%	–	Technical diploma or university degree

These data suggest a heterogeneous sample with a good level of professionalisation. The average age is 53 years, indicating a relatively high experience among the sample. The average farm size is substantial, at 42.5 hectares, suggesting significant land management responsibilities. Only 18% of the sample practices organic farming, highlighting that organic certification is still a minority. A relatively high share (35%) of farmers has higher education, indicating good technical or academic training. Furthermore, 64% of respondents report the presence of a successor, either active or expected, pointing to generational continuity in farm management.

3.5.6.2 Mixed Logit Model Estimation

The models' results are presented in tables 3.5.4 and 3.5.5.

Table 3.5.4: Results of the MLE

Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	z	MWTA (€)
Payment per hectare	0.004**	0.001	3.02	–
Duration (years)	-0.075***	0.021	-3.56	15.87

Effort required (impegno)	-0.126	0.121	-1.04	26.59
Payment type (100% result-based)	-0.371*	0.209	-1.78	78.00
Opt-out (no contract option)	-2.560**	0.820	-3.12	–

(**p < 0.05, ***p < 0.01)

The coefficients indicate that farmers are more likely to participate in agri-environmental programs when higher per-hectare payments are offered (positive and significant coefficient). Conversely, negative coefficients suggest that certain attributes decrease the likelihood of participation. Specifically, farmers show aversion to longer program durations and result-based payment, as these factors significantly reduce the probability of joining the program. Finally, the effort required in terms of income reduction is not statistically significant, suggesting it does not influence farmers' decisions.

Willingness-to-accept (MWTA) values provide further insight: farmers are willing to forego €15.87 per hectare to avoid longer program durations. They are also willing to give up €78 per hectare to avoid result-based payment.

Overall, the results highlight that financial compensation plays a crucial role, but minimising risk and ensuring flexibility are equally important to encourage farmer participation.

Table 3.5.5: Results of the MLE including interaction terms

Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	z	MWTA (€)
Payment per hectare	0.005**	0.001	2.94	–
Duration (years)	-0.081***	0.022	-3.70	16.32
Effort required (impegno)	-0.177	0.143	-1.24	35.35
Payment type (100% result-based)	-0.372	0.233	-1.60	74.13
Opt-out (no contract)	-2.151**	0.717	-3.00	–
Soil health perception × opt-out	3022**	1.051	2.87	–

(* p < 0.05, **p < 0.01)

The negative coefficient for the duration variable indicates that longer program durations decrease the likelihood of participation. The MWTA of €16.32 suggests that farmers would require an additional €16.32 per hectare to accept an extra year of program duration.

The Effort required variable has a negative but not significant coefficient, meaning increased effort requirements reduce participation probability. The MWTA of €35.35 implies that farmers need €35.35 more per hectare to compensate for the additional effort.

The coefficient for Soil health perception × opt-out is positive and suggests that farmers who perceive their soil as healthy are more likely to opt out of the program. This indicates a higher disutility associated with participation among these farmers.

3.5.6.3 Willingness to Accept (WTA)

The calculated WTA values indicate the compensation required to accept less favourable program conditions.

Table 3.5.6: Willingness to accept measurement

Attribute	MWTA (€)	95% CI
Additional years of commitment	15.87 €/ha	(6.93 ; 42.15)
Increase from low to medium and high-income reduction	26.59 €/ha	(-24.9 ; 118.9)
Switch to a 100% result-based payment	78 €/ha	(-10.90; 238.08)

These results highlight the need for higher financial compensation to convince farmers to accept less attractive program features. Farmers are relatively risk-averse and strongly value flexibility. For instance, they require an additional €15.87 per hectare to commit to longer durations, around €27 per hectare to offset expected income losses and approximately €78 per hectare to accept performance payment structures.

Programs that fail to address these concerns may face lower participation rates, even when offering some level of financial support.

3.5.7 Discussion and Conclusions

The results of this study offer insights into the preferences and behavioural patterns of Italian farmers regarding the adoption of soil-conservation agricultural practices through program mechanisms. Overall, the findings indicate a cautious attitude among farmers towards engaging in long-term conservation programs, particularly in the absence of flexible conditions and additional incentives. This observation aligns with similar studies conducted in other European contexts, suggesting an increasing trend of hesitancy in economic and structural concerns within the farming community.

One of the principal barriers to adoption identified by the analysis is the aversion to long-term commitments. Many farmers, especially those without a clear successor or intergenerational continuity on their farms, perceive extended program durations as limiting their autonomy and future decision-making capacity. This concern increases when programs lack options for early withdrawal or renegotiation. Therefore, introducing greater flexibility in the program's framework could be a crucial factor in enhancing the attractiveness of these schemes.

Another major obstacle is the perceived risk of income loss. Farmers often weigh the uncertainty of potential yield impacts or increased costs associated with conservation practices, even when financial compensation is offered. The estimated willingness to accept (WTA) values, in this study, highlight how much compensation farmers need to take less favourable program conditions, such as longer commitments or more restrictive payment mechanisms. Notably, the aversion to income loss appears to outweigh other considerations, suggesting that economic viability remains a dominant factor in decision-making processes.

Mixed payment mechanisms, which combine fixed and performance-based elements, appear to be a promising avenue for encouraging participation, since the result-based payment decreases the probability to participate. While these structures offer a potential balance between security and results-driven incentives, their successful implementation depends on building farmers' trust in monitoring systems and outcome evaluations. A lack of transparency or perceived complexity in these systems could undermine their effectiveness. Trust in the Institutions and clear communication are crucial in fostering confidence and acceptance.

The role of intermediaries, such as cooperatives, farmers' associations, agricultural consortia, and banks, emerges as a crucial element in bridging the gap between policy and practice. These actors can act as trusted facilitators, providing technical support and financial services. Their involvement can help overcome scepticism and build a sense of shared responsibility and community endorsement, particularly in areas where institutional trust is low or fragmented.

A set of operational recommendations can be drawn to increase the appeal of conservation programs further. Programs should allow for early withdrawal under specific conditions, reducing the perceived rigidity and risk. Accompanying each program with technical training and ongoing support can empower farmers and improve implementation outcomes. Moreover, transparent communication about the expected environmental and economic benefits is essential to align farmer expectations with policy objectives. Finally, involving local stakeholders in the design and adaptation of programs can ensure that they are sensitive to regional characteristics and farmer needs, enhancing their relevance and legitimacy.

In conclusion, the success of soil conservation programs in Italy, much like in other parts of Europe, will depend on the capacity to design flexible, trustworthy, and economically viable instruments. These programs must respond to farmers' practical realities, address their concerns transparently, and build institutional and social trust. Only by integrating these elements can such programs contribute

meaningfully to sustainable agricultural transitions and the broader goals of the European Green Deal.

3.6 Bulgaria

3.6.1 Synthesis of the results

Title: Stimulating the use of cover crops in traditional wine production in Bulgaria

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Structured Abstract: Introduction. This case-study targets the production and consumption of a traditional product (grapes and wine) in Bulgaria. The aim is to assess the attitudes of the respondents regarding the production of traditional local products (grape and wine), produced with and without agri-environmental measures focused on the prevention of soil erosion. The business model of interest is the value chain model where soil-improving practices in grape production can be stimulated through improved quality of the wine, and resulting increased opportunities and demand from wine tourism in Bulgaria. The specific agri-environmental measure that is chosen for the study is the application of cover crops as a way to reduce erosion and improve soil health. Cover crops have multiple benefits for the soil, including decreasing soil erosion, reducing soil compaction, and increasing organic matter. **Methods.** Interviews were conducted with the farm managers/owners of vineyards in the Plovdiv and Pazardzhik districts. The interviews took place in August, September and October 2024. A DCE is conducted to derive the willingness of farmers to participate in a scheme focused on this measure. Farm and farm characteristics (farm size, education, gender) are assessed to see whether they influence the willingness to participate. **Results.** Results show that price is an important determinant to stimulate participation. However, no significant results were found connecting the farm and farmer characteristics to the willingness to participate.

Key Words: cover crops, wine production

Case study: Traditional wine in Bulgaria

Incentives tested: Value chain payments for cover crops in wine production

Policy considered: Value chain payments (no policy)

3.6.2 Introduction

This case-study targets the production and consumption of a traditional product (grapes and wine) in the Plovdiv and Pazardzhik districts. The interviews with the farm managers/owners took place in August, September and October 2024. The aim is to assess the attitudes of the respondents regarding the production of traditional local products (grape and wine), produced with and without agri-environmental measures focused on the prevention of soil erosion. The business model of interest is the value chain model where soil-improving practices in grape production can be stimulated through improved quality of the wine, and resulting increased opportunities and demand from wine tourism in Bulgaria.

The specific agri-environmental measure that is chosen for the study is the application of cover crops as a way to reduce erosion and improve soil health. Cover crops are believed to have multiple benefits on the soil, including decreasing soil erosion, reducing soil compaction, and increasing organic matter. A DCE is conducted to derive the willingness of farmers to participate in a scheme focused on this measure.

3.6.3. Methodology

A DCE and a farmer survey was conducted. At the start of the interviews, farmers were informed that the aim of the survey is to analyse the production and consumption of traditional products (grape and wine) and rural tourism as a result of a new business model “Integrated Vineyard Production with Wine and Rural Tourism” in the Plovdiv and Pazardzhik districts. The aim was to assess the attitudes of the respondents regarding the production of grapes and wine with and without the use of cover crops. The survey took place in August, September and October 2024. The total number of participants in the survey is 55. The questionnaire was divided into three parts: Part A – General questions; Part B - Choice experiment Part C – Environmental questions.

In part B, respondents were confronted with choice cards containing two attributes (Table 3.6.1): (i) area enrolled in the contract; (ii) Levels of compensation for the additional environmental efforts. The DCE methodology involves creating an experimental design in which the different levels of the attributes are systematically combined to generate realistic but varied profiles. Each respondent makes a choice, allowing researchers to collect data on their preferences.

Table 3.6.1: Example of a choice card in the DCE

Attributes	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3	Option 4-Out
Area enrolled in the contract	30%	50%	100%	None of these. Stick to production without AEM.
Compensation for environmental efforts	67 euro per ha	102 euro per ha	152 euro per ha	

(planting cover crops)				
I prefer:	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3.6.4. Results

3.6.4.1 Descriptive analysis

The interviews covered all farms with vineyards and wine production in the two studied regions. Figures 4.6.1 – 4.6.4 show results of the descriptive analysis (55 respondents).

Figure 3.6.1: Age structure of the sample

Figure 3.6.2: Work experience of the managers in the sample

Figure 3.6.3: Farm sizes in the sample

Figure 3.6.4: Soil types in the sample

3.6.4.2 Analysis of questions related to the provision of ecosystem services from vineyards

One of the questions in the survey is referring to different aspects of soil quality as an ecosystem services. The respondents were asked to state which of three types of ecosystem services must be achieved through implementation of agri-environmental practices on the vineyards (Figure 3.6.5). All of the three ecosystem services are connected to different aspects of soil health - reducing soil erosion, increasing soil nutrients and increasing soil biodiversity. Both mechanical (erosion) and chemical (nutrients) condition of soils are of great significance for the production of grapes and wine. It is then not surprising that the results show that 83% and 80% of the respondents find it necessary to implement environmental measures for reducing erosion and increasing nutrients.

Figure 3.6.5: Soil ecosystem services

There are several agri-environmental measures that can be applied on vineyards to achieve the aforementioned ecosystem services. The respondents were asked to assess which of the four suggested measures could have a positive impact on their farm – cover crops, buffer strips, intermediate crops and drainage furrows (Figure 3.6.6). According to the results, the measure which is assessed with greatest impact is cover crops – 76% of respondents. On the other hand, it appears that buffer strips and drainage furrows are seen as the measures of greatest uncertainty – 61% and 55% respectively, said that they are not sure of whether this measure will have positive impacts on their farm, and 12% and 14% said that they don't want to apply these measures.

Figure 3.6.6: AES measures for soil health

Another ecosystem service taken into consideration is the cultural one. Here we have a question regarding several activities related to wine tourism as a type of cultural service (Figure 3.6.7). The predominant part of the respondents agrees with the mentioned activities. Three of the suggested activities are directly connected to the tasting of wines or visiting the wineries, where only one suggests additional tourist services specific to the area (horse riding, visiting eco trails, etc.). For the latter, about 24% of the interviewees don't know if this service will be applicable for their farm, perhaps being a little but outside of the core activities they have.

Figure 3.6.7: Wine tourism as a cultural service

Finally, one of the questions was targeting respondents' attitudes towards soil health and climate change in general. All of the respondents agree that climate change has a negative impact on their farms, that soil health is essential for them and they find it as an important factor for their productivity.

3.6.4.3 Analysis of the choice experiment and relationship with farm and farmer characteristics

The analysis examined how demographic factors—age, gender, education—and farm size influenced farmers' preferences for participating in an agri-environmental measure aimed at reducing soil erosion through the planting of cover crops (Figures 3.6.8 – 3.6.11). From a methodological perspective, Pearson's Chi-Square tests were used throughout the original study but were found to be limited due to small expected frequencies in many cells—well over the acceptable 25% threshold. This undermines the reliability of the results. The use of Fisher's Exact Test in follow-up analysis was more appropriate given the small sample sizes and sparse data. However, even with this correction, no demographic variable produced a statistically significant result at the 5% level.

Across all age groups, Option 3, which featured 100% participation in AEM and the highest compensation (€152/ha), emerged as the most preferred. This suggests a strong general interest in environmental sustainability. Gender-based analysis showed that both men and women prioritized Option 3, though men had slightly more varied preferences, with some also selecting tourism-related options. In the case of education, most respondents had a university degree and showed a moderate inclination toward Option 3. Interestingly, those with lower educational attainment were also likely to choose the sustainable option. Farm size also did not show a statistically significant association with option selection. Large farms (over 20 ha) did have a greater share of Option 3 selections, suggesting a possible link between more resources and willingness to adopt environmental measures.

Figure 3.6.8: Preferences by age

Figure 3.6.9: Preferences by gender

Figure 3.6.10: Preferences by education

Figure 3.6.11: Preferences by farm size

While no demographic factor yielded statistically significant differences in preferences for sustainable options, the data indicate a clear overall favourability toward environmental measures, especially Option 3. The strongest (though still non-significant) signal came from younger respondents, suggesting a possible generational shift in attitudes toward sustainability. Further research with larger, more balanced samples would be needed to confirm these trends.

3.6.4.4 Analysis of the choice experiment and respondents' perceptions of agri-environmental measures

One of the survey questions is targeting the perception of four different types of agri-environmental measures. The respondents were asked to assess which of the four measures could have a positive impact on their farm – cover crops, buffer strips, intermediate crops and drainage furrows. If we relate these answers with the choice of our four options in the choice experiment, we can observe the following outcomes:

- Regarding Option 1 (dedicating 25% of the total cultivated land for AEMs) the predominant part of the respondents accept all of the four AEMs as positive for their farm (the percentage is above 80%).
- Regarding Option 2 (dedicating 50% of the total cultivated land for AEMs) the measure cover crops is the one, where all of the respondents find acceptable and positive for their farm. In this option with the exception of cover crops, for the other three measures, nearly half or over the half of the respondents are not sure if these environmental measures are applicable and beneficial for their farm. Regarding the measure buffer strips almost 60% of the respondents are uncertain that the measure is beneficial for them, those results are 46% and 50% for intermediate crops and drainage furrows respectively.
- Regarding Option 3 (dedicating 100% of the total cultivated land for AEMs) the results are similar with those in Option 2 regarding cover crops. However, here the percentage of uncertain answers regarding the measures buffer strips and drainage furrows is the highest - 65% and 60% respectively. These are also the two measures, where almost one fourth of the respondents don't agree about the applicability on their farm.
- Those who opted out (the fourth option) are predominantly uncertain about any of the four measures.

Overall, we can conclude that the higher the land dedicated for AEMs, the lower the acceptance of buffer strips and drainage furrows as environmental measures. Cover crops appear to be the measure that is most acceptable in all of the options that accept to implement AEMs.

3.6.4.5 Analysis of the choice experiment and respondents' attitudes to soil quality

Another question of the survey that deserves attention is the one referring to the different aspects of soil quality as an ecosystem service. The respondents were asked to state which of the three types of ecosystem services must be achieved through implementation of agri-environmental practices on the vineyards. All of the three ecosystem services are connected to different aspects of soil health - reducing soil

erosion, increasing soil nutrients and increasing soil biodiversity. Several things can be observed here:

- For Option 1 (dedicating 25% of the total cultivated land for AEMs) where the dedication of land is the smallest percentage, respondents are not sure about the eco service increase of soil nutrients (almost 60%) and increasing soil biodiversity (40%). In contrast, all of the respondents find that reducing soil erosion must be achieved through AEMs on their farm.
- For Option 2 (dedicating 50% of the total cultivated land for AEMs) and 3 (dedicating 100% of the total cultivated land for AEMs) the answers are almost similar. Here, most of the respondents agree in highest percentage with the ecosystem services reduction of soil erosion and increase in nutrients (answers vary between 90-95%). However, with the service increase of soil biodiversity the percentage of disagreements is the highest – (15% for Option 2 and 18% for Option 3).
- For the opt-out option it is not surprisingly that the answers for all three types of ecosystem services are dominantly “unsure” or “don’t agree”. Where for the ecosystem services decrease of erosion and increase in nutrients the percentage of agreement is 41% and 48% respectively. For soil biodiversity all of the respondents are uncertain that this service should be achieved through AEMs on their farm. This leads to the conclusion that from all three types of ecosystem services biodiversity probably is the most understated and unacceptable from farmers’ perspective.

The overall conclusion is that the higher the land dedicated for AEMs, the higher the understanding and acceptance that ecosystem services must be achieved through environmental measures.

3.6.5. Conclusions

The analysis is targeting the production and consumption of traditional products (grape and wine). Our goal was to assess the attitudes of the respondents regarding the production of traditional local products (grape and wine), produced with and without agri-environmental measures focused on the prevention of soil erosion. We interviewed 55 managers/owners of farms with vineyards and wine production in Plovdiv and Pazardzhik districts in Bulgaria.

The following conclusion can be derived: The predominant part of the respondents find that reduction of soil erosion and increase of nutrients are important ecosystem services and must be achieved via implementing AEMs. However, to a lesser extent they have the same attitude towards increasing soil biodiversity. Probably, the lower level of agreement for this ecosystem service is due to the difficulty to comprehend its importance for soil health.

Regarding the positive impact of four agri-environmental measures - cover crops, buffer strips, intermediate crops and drainage furrows – respondents' answers showed that "cover crops" is the measure with highest acceptability among them. On the other hand, it appears that buffer strips and drainage furrows are seen as the measure of greatest uncertainty. One explanation for this outcome could be the level of technical difficulty for application of these two measures.

Regarding respondents' attitudes towards soil health and climate change all of them agree that climate change has a negative impact on their farms, that soil health is essential for them and they find it an important factor for their farms' productivity.

Regarding the choice experiment outcome, almost 70% of the respondents chose to dedicate half or all of their land to the implementation of AEMs (in our case cover crops). Regarding the attitude of farmers towards several AEMs (cover crops, buffer strips, intermediate crops and drainage furrows) the analysis showed that the higher the land dedicated for AEMs, the lower the acceptance of buffer strips and drainage furrows as environmental measures. Also, the higher the land dedicated for AEMs, the higher the understanding and acceptance that ecosystem services must be achieved through environmental measures.

Based on the analysis and the interviews, the following recommendations are made:

Increasing the specific knowledge of agricultural producers regarding environmental protection and provision of ecosystem services is of paramount importance. Some ecosystem services are very well recognized by the farmers like reducing soil erosion. The reason for this is not only the direct observation of the physical process, but also the effects it has on the farm productivity. On the other hand, ecosystem services like soil biodiversity is recognized by farmers to a lesser extent. Nonetheless, this service has an equal importance for farm productivity as well as soil erosion.

Provision of sufficient and appropriate compensation for implementation of AEMs. As we saw in the analysis almost half of the respondents agree to dedicate 100% of their farmland for introducing cover crops for the compensation level of 152 euro/ha. This is twice the compensation currently offered by the public payments.

Technical support for farmers for the accurate implementation of certain environmental measures. From the analysis for some measures, the acceptance level of farmers is relatively low as compared to cover crops for example. This might stem from the fact that adoption of these two measures is more difficult from technical perspective.

4 Joint Discussion

Five DCE experiments were conducted. They had different regional contexts, two DCEs were conducted in Germany, one in the Netherlands, one in Italia, and one in Bulgaria. The DCEs referred to different business models, offered different incentives, and had different underlying policies. The experiments for the Dutch, and one of the German (TUM) cases focused on incentives for carbon credits. The second German experiment (ZALF) and the Bulgarian experiment were on value chain incentives. The Italian case looked at combinations of incentives (agri-environmental schemes and carbon credit trade). Table 4.1. provides an overview of the case studies conducted.

A comparison of the case studies is difficult, and the results might not allow for a general conclusion regarding farmers' preferences for a business model type. For instance, the regional context might play a role. Dutch farmers are described to be difficult to motivate to extensify their practices as shown, for instance, for the participation in AES (Zimmermann & Britz, 2016). This can be explained by the high management intensities and higher opportunity costs when deciding about implementing soil health-friendly practices. These potentially also result in the low predicted probabilities observed in the Dutch carbon credit trade DCE.

In addition, the experiments' attributes were different. In the Dutch DCE only contract features (e.g., 'result-based payments' for carbon prices, or contract durations) are included as attributes. The measures that farmers must implement were fixed per farm type and did not vary. In other DCEs contract features and management requirements were included (e.g., cover crop requirements for the Bulgarian case). Table 4.1 displays the incentives included in the DCEs. All approaches (using contract attributes only, management requirements only, or a mix of both) are common in DCE on farmers' decisions to participate in contracts that seek to promote less intensive agricultural practices, as a review by Schulze et al. (2023) shows.

Table 4.1. Overview of the conducted DCE

Case	Business Model	Policy analysed	Incentives included	Pred. Probabilities
Rabo Carbon Bank (NL)	Carbon credit trade	Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU/2024/3012)	Fixed compensation of costs (%), carbon credit price, termination option for successors, free training, discount loans	40 %
CO2-Land (GER)	Carbon credit	Carbon Removals and Carbon	Fixed compensation of costs (%),	46%

		Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU/2024/3012)	carbon credit price, termination option for successors, free training, subsidies for investments	
AgoraNatura (GER)	Biodiversity & ecosystem service credits through online marketplace	Roadmap towards Nature Credits (initial step towards EU-level regulation)	Compensation of costs, credit price, monitoring options	-
Conservation agriculture (IT)	Public payments for sustainable practices	Common Agricultural Policy (AES)	Price, cost compensation, contract duration, result-based payment	-
Traditional wine (BG)	Value chain payments for soil-improving practices	Common Agricultural Policy (AES)	Price	-

Even though the contract requirements and the incentives varied, some joint conclusions might be possible when looking at the effects of specific attributes, and the included covariates (farmer and farm characteristics). The included attributes (incentives, commitments etc.) demanded by the contract and the effects found are summarized in table 4.2.

The literature review conducted in Work Package 2 showed that DCEs can include various monetary and non-monetary incentives. **The monetary incentives (fixed payments per hectare, result-based payments or premium prices paid to farmers) were significantly positively evaluated in all experiments.** Monetary attributes are described as decisive in multiple articles on the topic, e.g. for carbon credit trade (Canales et al., 2024; Shaikh et al., 2007), for AES (Schaub et al., 2023), or for value chain payments (Salazar-Ordóñez et al., 2021; Weituschat et al., 2023). These findings are also in line with the theoretical model, where farmers are expected to choose the option that offers the highest utility (Train, 2009), in a business management context, the utility of a business model strongly depends on the potential profits that are affected by the to-be-expected payments.

In some of the experiments **result-based, action-based or hybrid payments** were featured. These have different advantages and disadvantages (see Burton & Schwarz (2013) or Herzon et al. (2018) for an overview). Carbon credit trade commonly includes result-based payments (meaning that the payment is based on the amount of carbon stored). The experiments from the Netherlands, Italy and Germany (TUM) on carbon credit trade and the experiment on biodiversity credits traded on an online market place in Germany (ZALF) featured the different payment types. It became apparent that the risks entailed in result-based payments is negatively perceived, and that purely result-based payments can only attract few farmers. In the Dutch, both German and the Italian experiments, action-based or hybrid payments were also offered in some choice sets. Such hybrid payments might be possible when allowing combinations of payments from carbon credit markets and public payments. Comparing the DCE's results to the results of the policy innovation lab, this was to be expected, as the participants commonly highlighted that result-based payments are too risky (Bartolini et al., 2024).

Considering the experiment from the food **value chain**. The Bulgarian experiment found that price is an important determinant to stimulate participation but that farmers' attitudes and perceptions also matter and may differ between farm and farmer types. Looking at other sources, few articles consider value chain payments for soil health measures so far. One exception is the article by Weituschat et al. (2023). They evaluated farmers' willingness to participate in Barilla's sustainable farming initiative (food value chain payment), where farmers receive premium prices when farming more environmentally friendly. They found that some farmers are interested in such incentives, but that the incentive cannot attract those, for instance, valuing higher flexibility when making farm management decisions.

Finally, the NOVASOIL project also identified **public payments** for AES or eco-schemes as potential business models. The conducted DCEs do not focus on public payments alone, and only combine public action-based payments with other payments (e.g., in the German (ZALF) and Italian cases). This seems reasonable as a large body of literature on farmers' acceptance of public payments for soil health, or other less intensive practices exists (e.g, Barreiro-Hurlé et al., 2010; Jaeck & Lifran, 2014; Lapierre et al., 2023; Niskanen et al., 2021; Trenholm et al., 2017; Villanueva et al., 2017).

Besides the different payment types (action-based, result-based, hybrid) other non-monetary incentives were commonly featured. These included **training** opportunities in the Dutch and the German (TUM) experiment. They were found to promote the take up of the measures as well. However, the Dutch and the German cases show that training might not be equally valued across all groups. That training opportunities affect farmers' acceptance of contracts for public payments (Lapierre et al., 2023; Schaub et al., 2023), or contracts to participate in carbon credit markets (Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022) is described in the literature.

Buck & Palumbo-Compton (2022) reviewed the literature on farmers' willingness to adopt practices that lead to soil carbon sequestration. They point out that the literature on soil health practices is too limited to draw general conclusions. Still, they point out that the results indicate that an awareness of co-benefits is a strong driver of adoption and that better education and training opportunities can help.

In addition, some articles (e.g., Kragt et al., 2017) describe **access to credits** as important for farmers' decision to accept contracts. For carbon farming this might be because a payment for carbon credits can only be expected after carbon cumulated in the soil, and because investment costs can be high. Better access to credit helps farmers to finance the period between measure implementation and receiving a payment, or supports the investment in machinery necessary for soil health-friendly management. Access to credit as an incentive was investigated for the Dutch and the German (TUM) case-study but the effects were not found to be significant.

An interesting result of the experiments conducted is that the Dutch study and the German (TUM) study included a **termination option of contracts for successors**. They show that such options also hold potential to motivate farmers to opt for longer contracts. Farmers' reluctance to accept long contracts (longer than five years) is described as problematic for public payments by Harmanny & Schulp (2023) or Tiusanen et al. (2022). For carbon credit markets, Rochecouste et al. (2017) conducted interviews with farmers and found that they are not willing to limit the flexibility of themselves or their successors. Including termination options for successors could be an interesting option for all contracts in the business models researched (public payments, carbon credit markets, value chain payments).

However, offering such options might be challenging for the carbon credit trade business model. For carbon farming, reliable, long-term storage needs to be ensured. Whether contracts between farmers and buyers can include such options is, therefore, questionable. A suitable option might be to set up a contract between intermediaries

(e.g. farmer associations that implement carbon removal measures with their members), and the buyers. It might be easier for such intermediaries to build up buffers in case farms terminate contracts. Besides this, a **collective implementation** with groups is considered to hold further potential to motivate farmers to participate, in nature protection (Barghusen et al., 2021; van Dijk et al., 2015). Schaub et al. (2023) also describe a close relationship with peers as influential for the pick-up of public AES contracts.

Table 4.2. Overview of the included attributes in the DCE (and their effect).

	Rabo Carbon Bank (NL)	CO ₂ Land / Soil Fertility Fund (TUM, GER)	AgroNatura (ZALF, GER)	Traditional Wines (BG)	soil fertility (IT)
Incentive – Fixed, action-based payment (e.g. to cover the costs of a measure)	+	+	+	+	+
Incentive – Result-based payment (e.g. for carbon stored)	+	+			-
Incentive – Information on lower income volatility					
Incentive – Information on the expected farm income (e.g. prices at farm gate)					+
Incentive – Premium prices (through eco-labelling)					
Incentive – Bonus payments for reaching spec. quality or quantity					
Incentive – Collective bonus (for building networks)					
Incentive – Sharing of costs (production costs, specific asset costs)	+	+	+		
Incentive – Supply of inputs					
Incentive – Training and advice	+	+			
Incentive – Access to credit (discounts on loans, easier access to loans)	0	0			
Incentive – Co-benefits (soil fertility, less erosion, water holding capacity etc.)					
Incentive – Public recognition (e.g. labels, signs usable at farm gates)					
Commitments- Duration (contract length)	-	-			-
Commitments - Min. quantity requirements to enter a contract (e.g., hectares enrolled, soil type)					
Commitments – Management requirements (e.g. cover crops or red. tillage requirements)					

Others - Flexibility (termination options, options for renegotiation of measures / contract requirements)	+	+			
Others -- Management parties (e.g., monitoring and administration)			+		

Significantly positive effects are indicated with a +, significantly negative effects with a -, insignificant effects display a 0

Besides this, farmer and farm characteristics were included in (most) DCEs. They allow to learn which farmers are more or less likely to implement the business models. For instance, suppliers interested in value chain initiatives could use this information to identify farmers they can approach more easily. The results found for the covariates are summarised in Table 4.3. They refer to the results found for the average farmer.

The table is structured following a review by Dessart et al. (2019). The authors distinguish between dispositional factors, social factors, and cognitive factors. Dispositional factors are stable internal variables like personality, motivations, and beliefs. Social factors refer to farmers' engagement with others but also include social norms. Cognitive factors relate to learning and knowledge and are assumed to impact farmers' perception of the costs and benefits of measures. In addition to these personal factors, farm characteristics are included following Schaub et al. (2023) who focused on farms' structural features to provide information on the farmers' opportunity costs.

The result of Dessart et al. (2019) that better cognitive abilities promote farmers' engagement is confirmed for the Dutch, the Italian and the German (TUM) case. In addition, farmers' beliefs (e.g. regarding climate change) are commonly described to play a role (confirmed in the Italian and the Dutch case).

As expected, some DCEs also showed that farmers who farm more intensively are less likely to contract (e.g., the Dutch case). This was to be expected and is commonly described in review articles (Schaub et al., 2023). However, the finding remains challenging as more intensive farms create more negative effects on the environment.

Barreiro-Hurlé et al. (2010) find that farm features and contract features have a stronger importance when very demanding measures are required. When it comes to softer requirements with lower opportunity costs, personal factors play a larger role. The varying contract requirements might explain the heterogeneity across the experiments.

Table 4.3. Overview of the included covariates that significantly affected farmers' decisions in the DCEs.

	Rabo Carbon Bank (NL)	CO ₂ Land / Soil Fertility Fund (GER, TUM)	AgroNatura (ZALF, GER)	Traditional Wines (BG)	soil fertility (IT)
Farm structure – current soil management is soil health oriented	+				
Farm structure – Farm size (hectares, animals at farm ...)	-			0	
Farm structure – Farm profitability / Farmer income					
Farm structure – Management intensities (fertilizer usage, pesticide usage stocking rates, irrigation etc)	-				
Farm structure – Marketing options					
Farm structure – Rental and purchase prices for farmland					
Farm structure – Rental agreements					
Farm structure – Soil fertility	-				-
Farm structure – Farm type (e.g., mixed, dairy, arable)		-			+
Farm structure – Production type (organic, conventional)					
Cognitive abilities – Education & knowledge	+	+		0	+
Dispositional factors – Gender / Age (affect other features, e.g., beliefs)				0	+
Dispositional factors – Farm successor					
Social – cluster & peer relationship (information exchange with others e.g., through associations)			+		
Social – Seeking for technical advice					
Social – Trust in funding source (trust in contract parties)					+
Dispositional – Risk preferences					
Dispositional – Pro-Environmental attitude (experiences with AES, environment related beliefs (e.g., climate change))	+				+
Dispositional – Business orientation (statements on e.g., their evaluation of having freedom to operate)					-
Dispositional – Extraversion (Statements on their openness towards new experiences)					

Significantly positive effects are indicated with a +, significantly negative effects with a --, insignificant effects display as 0

5. Conclusions

Carbon Credit Trade – Regulation 2024/3012

- Carbon credit trade seems to be perceived as too risky (Bartolini et al., 2024), allowing hybrid payments might help to promote the take-up of such carbon credit trade as a business model
- **Hybrid payments** might be possible by allowing for combinations of action-based public payments and result-based payments from carbon markets.
- Overall, the potential of the business model to promote soil health needs to be critically evaluated, soil health measures are not among the preferred measures leading to carbon sequestration (European Commission, 2024), and doubts regarding their suitability to lead to long-term carbon sequestration are also described in the literature (e.g. Paul et al., 2023)
- **Collective implementation** of the business model might hold the potential to more easily fulfil some of the requirements set in 2024/3012, where the requirement for reliable quantification might entail substantial costs. Furthermore, a collective implementation approach might make it easier to provide buffers for leakage.
- The necessary long-term contracts for the business models could be promoted by offering **termination options** to successors, better **access to credit** might also help as farmers can expect a remuneration only after soil organic carbon has been sequestered, and initial investment costs are known to be a hindrance (Kragt et al., 2017)

Public Payments – AES & Eco-Schemes

- Public payments were not in the primary focus of any of the case studies. The literature on the topic is already rather large.
- However, public payments offer substantial funding, and hence their take-up should be researched and improved. Especially in countries with high opportunity costs, where the take-up is low (Zimmermann & Britz, 2016).
- The Dutch Q methodology experiment conducted for work package 2 shows this is not because farmers are uniformly uninterested in public payments, it rather seems that the payments on offer are perceived as too low to provide incentives. The high importance of the monetary compensation is confirmed in all experiments conducted for work package 4.

- Besides **better remuneration**, both collective implementation of AES, as already conducted in the Netherlands (Barghusen et al., 2021), and **termination options** to promote longer contracts that allow to reach more ambitious nature protection goals hold potential.
- Whether farmers will accept a stronger remuneration based on results, as foreseen by the European Commission, remains questionable. The results found in the literature appear to be mixed (Niskanen et al., 2021; Šumrada et al., 2021; Thiermann et al., 2023), **result-based payments** were perceived negatively in the conducted experiments.
- Besides a remuneration over eco-schemes or AES, the Dutch experiment offered a fixed compensation of costs that was described to cover the additional costs farmers face when switching to more soil health-friendly management (**payment for a transformation**). This was chosen as soil health-friendly management was found to result in higher incomes from farming in the long-term (Kik et al., 2024)
- Improved **education and training** on such positive effects might also help to boost their take-up. Better training opportunities were perceived positively in multiple case study DCEs, and soil health benefits are commonly described as decisive for farmers' decision to adjust their management (Buck & Palumbo-Compton, 2022; Cheye, 2023; Kragt et al., 2017; Tiusanen et al., 2022).

Value Chain Initiatives – Regulation for sustainability labelling on food

- Are perceived positively by some farmers in the Bulgarian, the German and other experiments in the literature (Weituschat et al., 2023). This may be because private contracts allow for relatively large flexibility (Thiermann & Dries, 2024).
- Research on the contracts promoting soil health appears to be scarce. An exception is an article by Weituschat et al. (2023), and as many other articles on farmer's acceptance of nature protection contracts, the article strongly focuses on the measures applied.
- For value chain payments further research could focus on **market power**, and how to ensure a fair remuneration of farmers. Besides this, it deserves attention whether consumers are also willing to pay a price premium in case ambitious claims such as 'climate neutrality' will not be possible. The EU **regulation regarding sustainability labelling** for the EU food sector is still in its development.

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